

Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean

Literature-Based Identification of Multi-Sectoral Water Management Approaches

VERSION 1.0

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Table of Contents

Literature-Based Identification of Multi-Sectoral Water Management Approaches	1
Introduction	9
1.1. Purpose.....	9
Integrated water resources management	10
2.1. Historical context.....	10
2.2. Definition of IWRM.....	11
2.3. IWWR implementation	13
Multi-objective and multi-sectoral approaches	14
3.1. Optimization concepts.....	15
3.1.1. Decision variables.....	16
3.1.2. Objective functions	16
3.1.3. Constraints	17
3.1.4. Non-dominated solutions to multiple conflicting objectives	18
3.1.5. Classification of optimization problems.....	21
3.2. Optimization approaches	22
3.2.1. Classical methods.....	25
3.2.2. Scalarization techniques	27
3.2.3. Multi-objective population-based algorithms	30
3.3. Simulation – optimization modeling.....	41
3.4. Conflict resolution methods	45
3.5. Applications in water management.....	47
3.6. Case studies.....	55
Conclusions and main perspectives for the future	59
References	60

List of Tables

Table 1 Websites and source codes of NSGA-II and NSGA-III and their variants - adopted from Ma et al. (2023).	37
Table 2 Primary datasets identified in papers related to water resource optimization. ...	54
Table 3 Examples of case studies about water resources optimization.	55

List of Figures

Figure 1 General Framework for IWRM (Loucks & van Beek, 2017).	12
Figure 2 Degree of integrated water resources management implementation (UNEP 2024).	14
Figure 3 Examples of unimodal, bimodal and multimodal peaks for a univariate unconstrained function showing the single, dual and multi-critical points, respectively ((Reddy & Henze, 2023).	17
Figure 4 Feasible region of solutions and constraints from a linear optimization problem (Jain & Singh, 2003).	18
Figure 5 (Left) Feasible domain with linear and nonlinear inequality constraints. (Right) Various local maxima and minima and global optimality - adopted from Yang (2021). ...	18
Figure 6 Example of two-dimensional decision space and two-dimensional objective space, the dominated solutions, and non-dominated solutions in the Pareto front (Bandaru et al., 2017).	20
Figure 7 Convergence and diversity criteria in the Pareto front. In the middle, as set of solutions that have converged onto the Pareto front but that are not too diverse; on the right, a set of solutions that have not converged but are diverse - adopted from Deb (2001).	21
Figure 8 Transformation curve (Pareto front) and indifference curves for two-objective optimization problem (Jain & Singh, 2003).	21
Figure 9 Classification of optimization problems (Yang, 2021).	22
Figure 10 Classification of main and most popular optimization techniques - adopted from Yang (2021) and Sharma & Kumar (2022).	24
Figure 11 Classification of main multi-objective optimization algorithm applied in water resource management - adopted from Yang (2021) and Sharma & Kumar (2022).	24

Figure 12 Piecewise linear approximation of a univariate function.	25
Figure 13 Convex region along the Pareto front that cannot be completely identified using the weighting method (Loucks & van Beek, 2017).	29
Figure 14 Application of the constraint technique for defining the Pareto front by maximizing one objective while constraining a second one to be no less than a specific value L_2 (Loucks & van Beek, 2017).	29
Figure 15 Schematic representation of (left) crossover and (right) mutation at a random location in genetic algorithms - adopted from Yang (2021).	31
Figure 16 Pseudo-code of a genetic algorithm (Yang, 2021).	32
Figure 17 Pseudo-code of NSGA-II (Sharma & Kumar, 2022).	34
Figure 18 Evolutionary multi-objective optimization software (Emmerich & Deutz, 2018).	39
Figure 19 General flowchart of the particle swarm optimization algorithm (D. Wang et al., 2018).	40
Figure 20 Coupling the simulation and optimization models (Karimanzira, 2016).	42
Figure 21 General optimization steps (Derepasko et al., 2021).	43
Figure 22 Water resource software and their application (Borden et al., 2016).	45
Figure 23 Evolution of the number of papers found in Scopus since 1992.	48
Figure 24 Word cloud of the keywords found in the selected papers.	49

Acronyms

DMP	Data Management Plan
WP	Work Package
CO	Consortium
PU	Public
R	Report
O	Other
DEM	Demonstrator
PT	Platform
NbS	Nature-based solution
MED	Mediterranean
UFZ	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research
RSS	Remote Sensing Solutions GmbH
UPV	Universitat Politècnica de València
IDRICA	Idrica
SEMIDE	Euro-Mediterranean Information System on know-how in the Water sector
TdV	La Tour du Valat
TUC	Technical University of Crete
UNIPR	Università di Parma
UNISS	University of Sassari
UNINA	University of Naples Federico II
RSCN	Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature
LPM	Living Planet Morocco
AGRI	AgroInsider
ESIM	Higher School of Engineering of Medjez El Bab
BU	Boğaziçi University
BMP	Best Management Practices

Executive summary

The overall objective of the "Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean" (OurMED) project is to design and explore innovative and sustainable storage and distribution systems tightly integrated into ecosystem management at the river basin scale. This is achieved by the combination of scientific and local knowledge, emerging from new and long-lasting spaces for social learning among interdependent stakeholders, society actors and scientific researchers in eight local and one regional MED demo sites. OurMED calls for a transition from a mono-sectoral water management approach based on trade-offs, to equitable multi-sectoral and integrative management that addresses all water bodies' capabilities and needs towards sustainability.

Task 4.1 of the OurMED project focuses on the development of a robust methodology for multi-objective water management at demo sites. A thorough literature review was conducted to inform this task, with a particular emphasis on recent approaches in water resources management. The review not only highlights methodologies, tools, and case studies but also serves as a milestone report, tracking the progress of Task 4.1.

Introduction

The “Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean” (OurMED) is an EU-funded project that operates under Grant Agreement Number 2222. The primary goal of the OurMED project is to design and explore innovative and sustainable storage and distribution systems tightly integrated into ecosystem management at the river basin scale.

OurMED recognizes the potential of integrating monitoring techniques, modeling approaches, and technological solutions to significantly improve our ability to develop effective water management strategies, with a focus on both natural and artificial water storage and distribution systems. To progress towards these objectives, one of the key tasks of the OurMED project (Task 4.1) is the development of a robust methodology using multi-objective functions for water management at the demonstration sites. This methodology will draw upon existing multi-objective and multi-sectoral water management practices and their relevant indicators, considering the specific climatic and ecological characteristics of the demonstration sites, as well as the needs of stakeholders.

To fulfil this task, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify the most used multi-objective and multi-sectoral water management approaches, as well as the tools and data utilised in such endeavours. Priority was given to the studies published in the last 10 years. However, important books and references about this topic were also used, as well as an attempt to present a general overview of the historical context and evolution of methods and technologies up to the present day.

We commence our review by examining Integrated Water Resources Management as a comprehensive and holistic framework that encompasses multi-objective and multi-sectoral approaches as integral components. Subsequently, we delve into the intricacies of multi-objective and multi-sectoral approaches, highlighting their focus on achieving diverse objectives across various sectors and exploring relevant methodologies and tools. Furthermore, we present case studies akin to the Demo Sites of the OurMED project to elucidate optimisation methods and illustrate their practical applicability in real-world scenarios. We also discuss prospects and areas for improvement within integrated water resources management. Lastly, we conclude and outline key perspectives moving forward.

1.1. Purpose

This document refers to the milestone of task 4.1 of the OurMED project, i.e., a literature review report on multi-sectoral water management (MSWM) approaches, and it serves as a critical means of verifying the progress of Task 4.1 towards the development of a robust methodology for multi-objective water management (MOWM) for each demo site, to be reported in deliverable D4.1.

This review will be a key tool for the OurMED project, as it brings together the main and most up-to-date concepts and discussions on multi-objective and multi-sectoral water resources management, as well as the main methods to solve complex water

management problems that commonly occur in regions that face conflicts between water resources availability and demand leading to challenging water and ecosystems problems.

Integrated water resources management

2.1. Historical context

For centuries, the management of water resources has been a longstanding practice (G. Wang et al., 2016). However, historically, this management has predominantly centered around isolated aquatic systems or individual water bodies within a basin, often neglecting a comprehensive consideration of all water resources and failing to embrace a holistic approach that acknowledges the interconnectedness of diverse ecosystems. IWRM has emerged as a response to the limitations and challenges posed by traditional sectoral and fragmented approaches to water resources management.

One of the earliest examples of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) is illustrated by the Tennessee Valley Authority (TVA), established in 1933. Beyond flood control and power generation, the TVA integrated considerations such as erosion control, recreation, and public health into its management strategies, reflecting aspects of today's IWRM approach (Snellen & Schrevel, 2004). In the mid-20th century, a United Nation report emphasized that water infrastructure alone does not ensure development, advocating for supporting services. However, integration then primarily focused on irrigation agriculture, neglecting other water uses until the 1980s (LNV, 2004). The 1977 International Water Conference in Mar del Plata underscored the need for coordination within the water sector and advocated for expanded irrigation agriculture. Yet, it overlooked concerns such as escalating water demand and environmental impacts. Issues raised in 1977, including equitable water supply, pollution control, and transboundary water management, remain pertinent today, emphasizing the ongoing relevance of integrated water management (UN, 1977).

Despite these previous efforts, according to UNESCO and NARBO (2009), IWRM gained significant attention starting from the 1980s when escalating demands for water across diverse user groups and economic sectors, alongside mounting pressures on existing water supplies. Moreover, concerns over widespread ecosystem pollution, climate change impacts, and subsequent declines in freshwater availability became increasingly salient issues, sparking ongoing debates.

Until that juncture, a universally recognized definition of the IWRM concept remained elusive. However, in 1992, the International Conference on Water and the Environment convened in Dublin, marking a pivotal moment where four guiding principles were established, enriching the discourse on the essence of IWRM (GWP, 2000). The four Dublin's guiding principles are:

- Fresh water is a finite and vulnerable resource, essential to sustain life, development, and the environment.
- Water development and management should be based on a participatory approach, involving users, planners, and policymakers at all levels.
- Women play a central part in the provision, management, and safeguarding of water.
- Water has an economic value in all its competing uses and should be recognized as an economic good.

Later, in the same year, these principles were expanded into several recommendations adopted in the Agenda 21 during the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED), in Rio de Janeiro. All countries should have established their own institutional bases for implementing IWRM, most of whose programs were expected to be completed by 2025.

In 2012, a report was compiled at the behest of the UN Commission on Sustainable Development to evaluate IWRM two decades after the UNCED Conference in Rio. Gathering responses from 134 UN member countries, it revealed that, since 1992, 80% of nations had initiated reforms to bolster integrated water management. The report highlighted an awareness of water-related risks and increased competition for resources. While countries adopting integrated approaches reported infrastructure advancements, there remained a need for improved coordination. Financing trends showed growth, but payment for water services lagged. Nonetheless, enhancements in institutional frameworks and policies led to more effective management practices and socioeconomic benefits. Emphasizing the significance of integrated water management in fostering a green economy, the report provided critical insights (GWP, 2013b).

In the last decade, IWRM was explicitly included as one of the targets of the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development defined by the Member States of the United Nations in 2015. Specifically, SDG 6.5.1, which focuses on implementing integrated water resources management practices at all levels, including through transboundary cooperation as appropriate (UN Environment, 2018). In the upcoming sections, we will explore the IWRM definitions, and the progress made by countries in the implementation of IWRM, highlighting key developments, challenges, and achievements in this critical endeavor.

2.2. Definition of IWRM

Over the last four decades, IWRM has become a prevailing paradigm among academics, policymakers, and practitioners within the water sector. As a management approach, IWRM encompasses a broad range of aspects, promoting a responsible use of water resources by considering cross-sectoral dependencies. Precisely because IWRM is a broad concept, it can be defined in several ways.

To translate the proposed principles and recommendations, and to help in the common understanding of the emerging concept of IWRM, in 2000, the Global Water Partnership (GWP) suggested the following definition:

“IWRM is a process which promotes the coordinated development and management of water, land, and related resources, in order to maximize the resultant economic and social welfare in an equitable manner without compromising the sustainability of vital ecosystems” (GWP 2000).

The International Water Association describes IWRM approaches as open and flexible processes which involve applying knowledge from various disciplines as well as the insights from diverse stakeholders to devise and implement efficient tools, equitable and sustainable solutions to water and development multi-sectoral problems. It should be a comprehensive and participatory planning that recognizes water as a natural resource with social, environmental, and economic values, and that ensures protection of ecosystems for future generations.

These concepts and definitions were illustrated by Loucks & van Beek (2017) in Figure 1.

Figure 1 General Framework for IWRM (Loucks & van Beek, 2017).

As per the GWP, IWRM incorporates management tools and methods that empower decision-makers to make logical and well-informed decisions among various alternatives. A diverse array of quantitative and qualitative methodologies is accessible, merging fields including economics, hydrology, hydraulics, environmental sciences, and sociology (Agarwal et al. 2000).

Finally, Borchardt and Ibisch (2013) indicate that, in IWRM, a hydrological assessment must be carried out to understand water reservoirs in basins, considering factors like land use, precipitation, runoff, and groundwater spanning sectors like economy, energy, agriculture, and environment, focusing on water quantity, quality, and demand. IWRM should address temporal and spatial water variability and mitigate risks from extreme events like droughts and floods, which can impact populations and economies, potentially worsening pollution.

2.3. IWRM implementation

IWRM stands as a pivotal framework in addressing the complexities of water management challenges in our rapidly changing world. As the demand for water continues to escalate due to population growth, urbanization, and climate change impacts, effective management strategies become increasingly imperative. At its core, IWRM emphasizes a holistic approach that considers the interconnectedness of social, economic, and environmental factors in water management decisions.

According to the GWP (2000), there is not a correct administrative model for IWRM. Instead, all regional and national institutions must develop their own IWRM practice by selecting, adjusting, and applying a suitable combination of tools based on specific circumstances. Furthermore, the implementation may take place on a step-by-step basis, considering the geographical scope, sequence, and timing of reforms. Strategies and framework for implementation can be adjustable for each situation according to experience; besides this, the whole process is unlikely to be rapid.

Implementing IWRM, as outlined by UNESCO (2009), requires that several key conditions are met. These encompass fostering political will and commitment to resolve stakeholder conflicts and enact legal and institutional changes. A basin management plan with a clear vision for water resource development, alongside the establishment of stakeholder participation and coordination mechanisms to facilitate involvement and information-sharing across all levels. Capacity development, particularly at the local government level. Also, the development of flexible water allocation plans, ensuring adequate investment, financial stability, and sustainable cost recovery mechanisms. Finally, the effective implementation cannot be ensured without a comprehensive understanding of natural resources, coupled with the establishment of robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to ensure an effective implementation.

IWRM implementation is progressively evaluated worldwide through the Sustainable Development Goal 6 (SDG 6), which is one of the 17 goals established in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, at the United Nations Sustainable Development Summit, in September 2015, with the aim of providing "peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and into the future."

The SDG 6 is to ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all by 2030, and one of its indicators tracks the degree of IWRM implementation, by assessing four key components of IWRM, such as 1) enabling environment; 2) institutions and participation; 3) management instruments; and 4) financing.

Figure 2 shows the current degree of IWRM implementation worldwide.

Figure 2 Degree of integrated water resources management implementation (UNEP 2024).

Unfortunately, none of the four IWRM components is expected to be fully implemented by all countries by 2030. Whereas management arrangements at the basin level are generally lagging behind at the subnational and national level, aquifer management is in an even more delicate situation (UNESCO, 2023).

G. Wang et al. (2016) remember that the IWRM implementation could become even more complicated since future watershed management will need to account for climate change impacts by employing technological advancements and holistic, cross-disciplinary approaches to ensure watersheds continue to serve their ecological, social, and economic functions.

As the current progress towards all the targets of SDG 6 is off-track, and in some areas the rate of implementation needs to quadruple (UNESCO, 2023), the SDG 6 Global Acceleration Framework (GAF) was created in 2020 as a part of the United Nations Secretary-General's Decade of Action to deliver the SDGs by 2030, aimed to deliver fast results, at an increased scale.

The SDG 6 GAF mobilizes UN agencies, governments, civil society, private sector, and other stakeholders around five cross-cutting and interdependent 'accelerators': financing, data and information, capacity development, innovation, and governance.

Multi-objective and multi-sectoral approaches

It is pertinent to introduce some clarifications regarding terms that will be utilized throughout the text. Multi-objective in water management (MOWM) is a set of techniques or methods for optimizing the various objectives involved in the management

of water resources in a certain region, city, sub-basins, or even just the water bodies within a company's site, without, necessarily, considering more than one sector that requires water demands (Gao et al., 2014; Farahi et al., 2021). Multi-sectoral water management (MSWM) strategies, however, account for more than one sector (agricultural, industry, domestic, environmental, etc.) dependent on water demands whose water resources are usually part of broader regions, watersheds at larger scales, in a regional, national, or international scope (Yamout & El-Fadel, 2005; Xevi & Khan, 2005a; Janus et al., 2023; Guo et al., 2024).

While both MOWM and MSWM approaches can contribute to the implementation of IWRM, it is crucial to recognize that they have distinct meanings from IWRM, albeit being complementary. While sharing common principles like integration, stakeholder participation, adaptive management, and sustainability, MOWM and MSWM focus primarily on achieving multiple objectives across various sectors. In contrast, IWRM adopts a broader, more holistic perspective, encompassing the entirety of water resources management involving technical, economic, financial, and institutional aspects (Loucks & van Beek, 2017).

To conduct a comprehensive literature review aimed at identifying multi-objective and multi-sectoral water management approaches, along with the tools and data employed, this section will commence with a review of fundamental optimization concepts, classifications, and methods. Subsequently, we explore an extensive literature review of the subject and its practical application in water resources management. Finally, we offer a brief overview of commonly utilized tools in simulation optimization tasks for water resources management.

3.1. Optimization concepts

Optimization methods are techniques used to obtain the results that best meet requirements and previously established objectives disregarding worst-case scenarios. Optimization is basically described as ways of mathematically representing the operational objectives of a system which can be solved by computers and programming languages. In general, optimization models are used to maximize or minimize one or more objective functions, i.e., to find the best or most suitable and viable alternative for solving a problem (Karimanzira, 2016; Loucks & van Beek, 2017; Emmerich & Deutz, 2018; Derepasko et al., 2021).

Although optimization methods use simplified ways to represent the processes and interactions of a real system, they are very useful for solving problems by filtering out many alternatives, as well as generating previously unknown alternatives by decision-makers. However, caution and experience are required when analyzing the results, as local solutions may not be the same as globally optimal solutions, besides very optimistic solutions may not be technically feasible (Mirchi et al., 2011).

Optimization methods have found application across diverse areas, including socio-economic, engineering, and environmental (Nagel, 2000; Ali & Sik, 2012; Singh, 2012; Lauinger et al., 2016; Sioshansi and Conejo 2017). Depending on the complexity of the problem, the optimization can take the form of single or multi-objective methods. Real-world challenges often entail diverse and conflicting objectives, prompting the application of these methods across various domains such as data mining, tourism management, energy, mechanical engineering, bioinformatics, and environmental management (Liu et al., 2020; Abdallah et al., 2021; Arbolino et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2021; Tian et al., 2021; Jalili et al., 2022).

In any optimization problem, whether it involves a single objective or multiple objectives, certain fundamental components are typically present: decision variables, objectives functions, constraints, and optimal or non-dominated solutions.

3.1.1. Decision variables

The decision variables are independent numerical variables, denoted as

$$X = [x_1 x_2 \dots x_D]^t, x \in \mathbb{R}^D \quad (1)$$

where X is a vector of x_i decision variables in a D -dimensional decision space \mathbb{R}^D , which can be any design or operating policy variable which the decision-makers can control or adjust in a system to reach the desired goals (Loucks & van Beek, 2017; Sharma & Kumar, 2022). They can be real continuous, discrete or a mix of these two (Yang 2021). Hence, during an optimization problem, the values of the decision variables are systematically changed within their feasible range usually limited by constraints (Jain & Singh, 2003) to find the optimal solution. The space defined by the decision variables is known as the decision space or search space (Yang 2021).

3.1.2. Objective functions

The formulation of the objective function is one of the most critical phases of an optimization problem as it represents the performance level valuation obtained by the set of decision variables, which define how a system is to be operated (Sharma & Kumar, 2022). It represents the goal of the optimization problem and should be given explicitly, such as

$$f(x) = a_1 x_1 + a_2 x_2 + \dots + a_n x_n \quad (2)$$

where $f(x)$ is an example of a linear objective function, x_i are the decision variables, and a_i a set of coefficients that depend on the optimization problem (Jain & Singh, 2003). The space determined by the objective function values is referred to as the solution space or objective space (Yang 2021). It is important to remember that optimization is referred to maximize or minimize a function, i.e., attempt to reach the best feasible solution inside the objective space. For example, if a function is unconstrained, unimodal convex or concave, its minimum or maximum would be the solutions where the first derivative or slope of the function equals zero. Reddy & Henze (2023) present in Figure 3 some

examples of unimodal, bimodal and multimodal functions of single decision variables, which is important for understanding the local and global optimal solutions.

Figure 3 Examples of unimodal, bimodal and multimodal peaks for a univariate unconstrained function showing the single, dual and multi-critical points, respectively ((Reddy & Henze, 2023).

The formulation of objective functions regarding the number of variables and the nature of the problem (e.g., if they are linear or non-linear, unimodal or multimodal functions) may affect directly on the computational effort to solve a problem, as well as the number of objectives functions in multi-objective problems (Loucks & van Beek, 2017). Hence considerable efforts may be needed as the objective functions should be carefully formulated, and properly reflecting the preference of the decision-maker (Jain & Singh, 2003).

In water resource optimization problems, they can be formulated in various forms considering economic, social, and environmental criteria, and should incorporate measures such as efficiency and sustainability, among others (Karimanzira, 2016).

3.1.3. Constraints

The constraints are also represented by mathematical expressions, such as

$$g_j(x) = a_{1j}x_1 + a_{2j}x_2 + \dots + a_{nj}x_n \leq b_j, j = 1, \dots, m \quad (3)$$

Where $g_j(x)$ is an example of an inequality linear constraint out of a set of m constraints. They are intended to force the optimization model to obey physical laws or operational, socio-economic and political requirements, i.e., they restrict the range over which the decision variables can change, and thus affect the optimum solution (Jain & Singh, 2003).

If the number of constraints is zero, the optimization is called unconstrained. In general, objective functions and constraints are not necessarily differentiable and can be linear or nonlinear, continuous or discrete, and analytic or procedural (Karimanzira, 2016).

According to Strauch et al. (2019), the constraint functions can significantly influence the optimization outcomes, reducing computational time, in addition to providing more realistic results. However, it's important to note that the feasible region, encompassing all values satisfying the constraints, is where we search for the optimal solution. With multiple constraints, this region can become complex and irregular, making it harder to achieve true optimality (Yang 2021). Derepasko et al. (2021) give some examples of the

nature of constraints regarding water resource optimization problems, such as (1) the system state, e.g., conservation of mass; (2) supply-related, linked to the magnitude, timing, and type of demand; (3) infrastructure-related (e.g., design or operational capacity of dams and hydropower plants); and (4) regulative, which are defined based on policies or normative requirements.

Figure 4 shows the feasible region of an optimization problem, where the constraints are linear. Once the feasible region is identified, if the optimization function is linear, it is quite simple to find the optimal point since it will lie in one of the corner points. Jain & Singh (2003) point out that this graphical method can be used to solve only linear problems involving at most two decision variables.

Figure 4 Feasible region of solutions and constraints from a linear optimization problem (Jain & Singh, 2003).

The complexity of the optimization problem increases if there are nonlinear objective functions or constraints, or when they behave as multimodal optimization problems as shown in Figure 5. Yang (2021) shows an example of a nonlinear objective function with various local maxima and minima (F, A, C), and the global optimality (maximum D and minimum E). One should be careful when evaluating the solutions as some optimization methods do not provide or are not capable to search for the global optimum.

Figure 5 (Left) Feasible domain with linear and nonlinear inequality constraints. (Right) Various local maxima and minima and global optimality - adopted from Yang (2021).

3.1.4. Non-dominated solutions to multiple conflicting objectives

As the optimization models are usually used to maximize or minimize one or more objective functions, a multi-objective optimization problem (MOP) can generally be written as:

$$\text{Max } F(x) = f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_n(x), x \in \mathbb{R}^D \quad (4)$$

where $F(x)$ is the vector of objective functions $f_i(x)$, which returns a vector composed of the solutions of each objective. Finding its maximum imply identifying the fittest solutions for each objective function. In this case, the optimization approaches attempt to optimize a vector of objective functions and not a scalar (Deb, 2001).

Since there might be two or more conflicting objectives in multi-objective optimization, i.e., when the components of the $F(x)$ vector compete, there will not be just one global solution to the problem. In such a case the solutions should be sought considering the trade-offs between the different objectives (Karimanzira, 2016). That is why the final decision must be based on qualitative and quantitative information, in a political and social process, and not by a computer (Loucks & van Beek, 2017).

For that purpose, the Pareto Optimum concept is used to obtain the most efficient and feasible solutions. According to the Edgeworth-Pareto principle, the concept of optimum is based on the intuitive idea that an optimal solution should be such that no other solution can improve one objective without worsening at least one other objective. These solutions are known as non-dominated solutions.

A simple example could clarify what a non-dominated solution is. Imagine you're choosing between snacks based on their tastiness and healthiness. A non-dominated snack is one that isn't worse than any other snack in both tastiness and healthiness. So, if you have a snack that is just as tasty as others but healthier, or just as healthy but tastier, it's a non-dominated choice. You can't find another snack that beats it in both aspects. It's like picking the best compromise without losing out completely on either taste or health. There may be snacks that are healthier or tastier, but not both healthier and tastier.

The set of all non-dominated solutions defines the Pareto front. Bandaru et al. (2017) presented in Figure 6 an example of a two-dimensional decision space and a two-dimensional objective space (where the objective is to minimize both objective functions). The Pareto front is given by the dotted line, there is no point within the decision space for which the objective functions will beat simultaneously any of the points in the Pareto front. The ideal point would be one that has the minimum value for both functions and the nadir point (or worst point) would be the one with the largest values for both functions.

Figure 6 Example of two-dimensional decision space and two-dimensional objective space, the dominated solutions, and non-dominated solutions in the Pareto front (Bandaru et al., 2017).

The Pareto-optimal front is obtained by plotting the non-dominated solutions according to their objective values, yielding an M -dimensional surface where M is equal to the total number of objectives (John et al., 2010). Yang (2021) comments that the main difficulty to adapt an algorithm from solving single-objective optimization to accommodate multiple objectives is the requirement to account for the dominance of each candidate solution.

Emmerich & Deutz (2018) point out that optimization problems with more than 3 objectives may be termed as many-objective optimization problems (MaOP). These problems should use specific techniques, firstly because they cannot be visualized in conventional 2D or 3D plots, the complexity of problems becomes too high, requiring high computation effort, and the ratio of non-dominated points tends to increase rapidly with the number of objectives.

For Deb (2001), multi-objective optimization analysis should focus on two main goals, which are to find a set of solutions as close as possible to the Pareto front and to find a set of solutions with the greatest possible diversity. While convergence refers to dominance criterion, i.e., solutions closer to Pareto front, where there can only be non-dominated solutions, diversity provides a larger spectrum of possible solutions for the optimization problem. Figure 7 illustrates the two concepts of convergence and diversity, which can be conflicting, therefore, both must be taken into account when evaluating the performance of an optimization algorithm. It shows that Algorithm A is better than Algorithm B in terms of convergence. On the other hand, Algorithm B is better in terms of diversity.

Figure 7 Convergence and diversity criteria in the Pareto front. In the middle, as set of solutions that have converged onto the Pareto front but that are not too diverse; on the right, a set of solutions that have not converged but are diverse - adopted from Deb (2001).

Jain & Singh (2003) present Figure 8 with an example of possible trade-offs when analysing two objective functions and two decision variables. The management goals should lie on the transformation curve since this is the set of non-dominated solutions or efficient trade-offs. Despite point M is in the feasible region, it represents a worse solution since there are better values of objective functions by moving to point B or C. The indifference curves represent the equal preference of a decision-maker, considering that there may be different sets of indifference curves depending on each decision-maker. The optimal plan would be point F since it is the one on the objective transformation curve which achieves the highest level of preference of the decision-maker.

Figure 8 Transformation curve (Pareto front) and indifference curves for two-objective optimization problem (Jain & Singh, 2003).

3.1.5. Classification of optimization problems

Figure 9 presented by Yang (2021) shows some examples of how the optimization problems can be classified. They can be multimodal or unimodal problems. They can be

deterministic (when there is no uncertainty in the variables or the objective functions) or stochastic. They can be continuous and discontinuous. Reddy & Henze (2023) highlight that classical calculus-based methods can break down if there are discontinuous objective functions, requiring advanced methods such as metaheuristics. Discontinuity may arise when one or more variables are discrete against continuous, which would fall under the classification known as integer or discrete programming.

In the following sections we will consider some of these terms to discuss the characteristics of each optimization approach and what type of problems they can solve.

Figure 9 Classification of optimization problems (Yang, 2021).

3.2. Optimization approaches

There are two main categories 1) classical optimization methods, such as linear programming, non-linear programming and dynamic programming (Jain & Singh, 2003; Pedregal, 2004; Karimanzira, 2016; Loucks & van Beek, 2017; Reddy & Henze, 2023); and 2) heuristics and metaheuristics techniques, such as population-based techniques (Horne et al., 2016; Bandaru et al., 2017; Emmerich & Deutz, 2018; Yang, 2021; Kumar & Yadav, 2022; Sharma & Kumar, 2022)

Classical optimization methods encompass techniques designed to ensure the discovery of an optimal solution. These methods typically do not necessitate multiple iterations or parameter adjustments through trial and error. However, it's worth noting that exact techniques are more likely to have limited applicability in real-world and more complex scenarios, as well as they should be combined with other strategies or scalarization techniques to address multiple conflicting objectives (Rauschenbach et al., 2016).

Although classical optimization methods are still used, the most recently developed optimization methods are based on stochastic techniques that attempt to convert observed inputs into observed outputs using a set of mathematical equations and expressions for the estimation of their parameters, such as the heuristic and metaheuristic approaches. They do not describe physical processes but serve as substitutes for more mechanistically or process-based models which computational speed is critical or where the underlying relationships are poorly understood or too complex to be easily incorporated into calculus-based, linear, nonlinear, or dynamic programming models (Loucks & van Beek, 2017). These techniques are increasingly used because they allow complex optimization problems to be solved that are not possible using classical methods (Yang, 2021; Kumar & Yadav, 2022; Reddy & Henze, 2023).

According to Yang (2021), there is a small difference between heuristic and metaheuristic techniques. Heuristic also known as “to find” or “to discover by trial and error” is a set of techniques used to increase the performance of a search process and find reasonably good solutions in a short time, but there is no guarantee that optimal solutions will be reached, neither that all algorithms will work in all situations. Osman & Laporte (1996) defined metaheuristic as an iterative generation process which guides a subordinate heuristic by combining intelligently different concepts for exploring and exploiting the search space and uses learning strategies to structure information in order to find efficiently near-optimal solutions. The metaheuristic are high-level strategies to increase heuristic performance in a more “intelligent” and biased form than just providing random initial solutions.

Metaheuristic techniques do not require detailed knowledge of problem physics, as well as they excel at handling complex, multi-modal, discontinuous, and high-dimensional problems, providing near-optimal or satisfactory solutions (Yang 2021; Beiranvand & Ashofteh, 2023; Reddy & Henze, 2023).

These techniques also can be broadly categorized into deterministic and probabilistic approaches (Sharma & Kumar, 2022). Despite that, probabilistic approaches have much a more applicability and greater number of existing methods to solve single optimization problems, or multi-objective optimization problems (MOPs) with some adjustments (Yang, 2021). Metaheuristic algorithms can further be classified into single-solution-based or population-based techniques. Single-solution-based methods focus on manipulating and refining a single solution throughout optimization, while population-based methods operate on a set of solutions or individuals, promoting diversity within the search space (Emmerich & Deutz, 2018; Kumar & Yadav, 2022; Sharma & Kumar, 2022).

It should be noted that all optimization techniques can be more powerful when used in conjunction with simulation models (Karimanzira, 2016; Loucks & van Beek, 2017; Derepasko et al., 2021; Iman et al., 2021; Cai et al., 2022).

Given that probabilistic-population-based approaches are efficient and more commonly used to solve multi-objective optimization, this literature review should focus on that category, although the primary classical methods will be also briefly discussed. Key references will be provided for readers interested in delving deeper into these topics. Moreover, emphasis will be placed on methods commonly employed in water resources management as this literature review is pivotal in shaping a methodology to this field.

Figure 10 shows the classification of the main and most popular optimization techniques, whereas Figure 11 focuses on multi-objective optimization algorithms, both based mainly on the classification proposed by Yang (2021) and Sharma & Kumar (2022), but also taking into account others references, such as (Bandaru et al., 2017; Loucks & van Beek, 2017; Emmerich & Deutz, 2018; Kumar & Yadav, 2022; Beiranvand & Ashofteh, 2023).

Figure 10 Classification of main and most popular optimization techniques - adopted from Yang (2021) and Sharma & Kumar (2022).

Figure 11 Classification of main multi-objective optimization algorithm applied in water resource management - adopted from Yang (2021) and Sharma & Kumar (2022).

3.2.1. Classical methods

Although this literature review focuses on multi-objective optimization, it is important to understand classical optimization methods, as they serve as the foundation of optimization techniques and for the development of more recent methods. Besides, they are still broadly used in the field of water resources management as single objective optimization or scalarized multi-objective optimization that will be mentioned in the following sections (Rauschenbach et al., 2016; Loucks & van Beek, 2017).

Within the classical methods those with more relevance in the field of water resources are Linear Programming (LP), Non-linear Programming (NLP), and Dynamic Programming (DP)(W, 2004; Karimanzira, 2016; Loucks & van Beek, 2017). Linear programming deserves to be highlighted due to its numerous applications in the management and planning of water resources (Karterakis et al., 2007; Yoo, 2009; Kermani et al., 2014; Yue et al., 2022; Housh, 2023), being still one of the most popular and commonly applied optimization algorithms in practical use today (Loucks & van Beek, 2017). It was developed by G.B. Dantzig in 1947 to solve logistics problems for the American Air Force. Its application in water resources began in the 1960s as part of the work of the Harvard Water Resources Group (Dantzig, 2002).

As its name implies, LP requires linear relationship between the decision variables and the objective function. However, even when there is a non-linear relationship, LP can be employed with the aid of linearization processes or iterative procedures (Jain & Singh, 2003). One such method is the Piecewise Linearization (Figure 12), which consists of dividing the non-linear objective function into several linear segments. It is used for minimization problems of convex non-linear objective functions, or for maximization problems of concave functions. The smaller the linear segments, the better the representation of the function. However, each segment corresponds to a new function formulation, increasing the size of the problem as new segments are created.

Figure 12 Piecewise linear approximation of a univariate function.

Another technique used to solve non-linear programming problems is the Sequential (or successive) Linear Programming (SLP), which uses LP in an iterative search for the optimum. Once an initial point has been determined, the objective function and its constraints are linearized around this point. The solution obtained is used as a new point around which the objective function is linearized again, and this process continues until the convergence criterion is reached (Karimanzira, 2016).

According to Karimanzira (2016), the application of LP has some advantages, such as (i) flexibility and ability to adjust and solve large-scale problems; (ii) achieving the global optimum values; (iii) well-developed duality theory for sensitivity analysis; and (v) the existence of many computational packages ready to use. Linear programming procedures or algorithms for solving linear optimization models are often the most efficient ways to find solutions to very large optimization problems containing many variables and constraints. According to Reddy & Henze (2023), the Simplex algorithm is the most popular numerical technique for solving linear optimization problems with a large set of linear constraints.

With regard to Non-Linear Programming (NLP), it can be classified as analytical techniques, in which the optimal solutions are obtained by solving systems of equations, or through numerical search techniques by using past information in an interactive optimization process (Pedregal, 2004). According to W (2004), most robust methods are the successive linear programming (SLP), successive quadratic programming (SQP), augmented Lagrangian method, and the generalized reduced gradient (GRG). Karimanzira (2016) point out that GAMS/MINOS is one of the most successful software packages to solve problem with nonlinear constraints and objective function. However, LANCELOT also has been one of the successful software packages based on Trust Region algorithms and designed for the purpose of general nonlinear programming problems, and IPOPT is an efficient, freely available optimization solver suitable for large-scale and highly-structured problems, which uses nonlinear interior point algorithm to solve general nonlinear programming problems.

One great advantage of NLP is its coverage-range that offers a more general mathematical formulation and does not require simplification procedures, increasing the precision of the results. However, the optimization process is usually slower than other methods, such as simple LP, since the mathematics involved in non-linear models is much more complex than in LP cases, thus requiring more processing time. Furthermore, NLP often requires continuous variables, continuous and differentiable objective and constraint functions, and the effort needed to find a solution may be strongly influenced by the number of constraints and the characteristics of the objective function (Karimanzira et al., 2016; Mandal, 2023).

Another classical optimization method is Dynamic Programming, which consists of a multi-stage sequential decision process based on Richard Bellman's Principle of Optimality, i.e., whatever the current state and past decisions leading up to it, the

remaining decisions must constitute an optimal policy (Reddy & Henze, 2023). DP models involve states, stages, and decisions. A stage could be time intervals or spatial intervals at which a decision must be made, whereas a state variable typically represent some existing condition, and is graphically represented as a node in the optimization process, which is linked by the decisions one could make to get from one state (node) to another. The discrete dynamic programming algorithm attempt to find the best path through this network, by breaking down more complex problems involving several variables of discrete processes or continuous functions into a sequence of simpler stages, each of them involving a singular variable. Hence, instead of solving the entire problem at once, these simpler stages are solved one after the other (Loucks & van Beek, 2017).

Loucks & van Beek (2017) also point out that DP problems can be solved with backward-moving algorithm or forward-moving algorithm, depending on the data available and strategies adopted by decision makers, however, in some problems, only the backward-moving algorithm produces a useful solution. If the return at any stage is dependent on the decisions made at other stages, DP becomes more difficult to apply. In other words, optimality assumes the decision policy for the remaining stages is independent of the decisions adopted in previous stages, although the subsequent choices are affected by earlier ones (W, 2004).

Next to linear programming, DP has been one of most popular optimization techniques applied to water resources management, as it can overcome difficulties regarding nonlinear, nonconvex, and discontinuous objective and constraints functions, unlike the previous classical methods (W, 2004).

In respect to the disadvantages of using DP, computational time can grow exponentially with the number of state variables, which is called the "curse of dimensionality", and users usually need to write a computer program or software to solve a particular problem. Besides, it could be difficult to structure the problem so that it fits the dynamic programming network format (Loucks & van Beek, 2017). Finally, DP models can be applied to design problems or to operating problems, but seldom to problems having both unknown decision variables of design and operating policy at the same time.

According to Feng et al. (2023), several DP variants have been developed to alleviate the dimensionality problem, such as progressive optimization algorithm, dynamic programming successive approximation, and discrete differential dynamic programming. However, they remain sensitive to the initial operation trajectory, which makes it challenging to ensure a globally optimal solution. For that reason, they presented a long short-term memory (LSTM) approach based on approximate dynamic programming (ADP) to overcome this problem.

3.2.2. Scalarization techniques

Multi-objective optimization approaches attempt to optimize a vector of objective functions and not a scalar (Deb, 2001), since it is not possible to optimize all conflicting

objectives without worsening another, trade-offs and compromises between objectives are required (Yang 2021). Furthermore, objectives may be incomparable, thus an optimal solution cannot be found since all feasible solutions are not comparable. It means no particular non-dominant solution can be identified as preferable to any other non-dominant solution. In such a case, a complete order of priority can be obtained for a vector optimization only by introducing value judgments into the solution process (Jain & Singh, 2003).

For this reason, scalarization techniques have been developed to transform a problem with multiple non-commensurate and conflicting objectives into a scalar problem in which the objectives are ranked in order of priority (Emmerich & Deutz, 2018). In fact, all multi-objective optimization techniques could be evaluated as one composite (scalar) objective once a relative worth or utility is set for each objective (Jain & Singh, 2003).

According to Emmerich & Deutz (2018), scalarization implies that the objective functions are aggregated or reformulated as constraints, resulting in a constrained single-objective problem. Two of the most popular approaches are the Weighting and Constraint techniques.

The Weighting method basically relies on converting the objective vector into a scalar optimization problem by assigning relative weights to each objective function and summing them. The general equation can be written as

$$\text{Max } F(x) = w_1f_1(x) + w_2f_2(x) + \dots + w_nf_n(x) \quad (5)$$

which can be subject to constraints, such as

$$g_j(x) = a_{1j}x_1 + a_{2j}x_2 + \dots + a_{nj}x_n \leq b_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, m \quad (6)$$

where the nonnegative weights w_i are given constants. Thus, the problem could be solved using any classical optimization method, such as Linear Programming, or any other metaheuristic techniques listed in section 3.2.3.

By parametrically varying the weights in the objective function over reasonable ranges, a wide range of plans with different priorities can be built. The trade-offs or marginal rate of substitution of one objective for another at each solution on the Pareto front is explicitly specified by the relative weights, making value judgments necessary. When dividing each objective value by its maximum possible value, the weights can range from 0 to 1 and sum up to 1, to reflect their relative importance. Loucks & van Beek (2017) remember that the Weighting approach cannot generate the complete set of efficient plans unless the Pareto front is strictly concave for maximization (or convex for minimization) in the sense that only the endpoints of a convex region could be identified (Figure 13).

Figure 13 Convex region along the Pareto front that cannot be completely identified using the weighting method (Loucks & van Beek, 2017).

In respect to the Constraint technique, it replaces all the objective functions with lower bound constraints, except one that would be the single objective function. The non-inferior solution can be identified by taking a different objective function each time and solving the single objective optimization problem. Unlike the previous technique, the constraint approach can find the entire set of efficient plans for any shape of Pareto front, which is defined by solving the model many times for many values of the lower bounds. Figure 14 illustrates the constraint method for identifying the Pareto front by maximizing one objective while constraining a second one.

Figure 14 Application of the constraint technique for defining the Pareto front by maximizing one objective while constraining a second one to be no less than a specific value L_2 (Loucks & van Beek, 2017).

The number of solutions to a Weighting or Constraint technique can be reduced substantially when the acceptable weights or lower limits can be identified by the participants in the planning and management process. Moreover, interactive methods

can modify the techniques mentioned above to reduce the computational effort as well as the amount of uninteresting information to decision makers (Loucks & van Beek, 2017).

Cho et al. (2017) give a consistent overview about many other scalarization techniques, and compare each one by describing their pros and cons in the optimization process, such as Goal Programming, Utility function method, Achievement function method, Benson's method, etc.

It is important to remember that the set of non-dominated solutions can change depending on the priority or relevance of each objective. Moreover, some methods and techniques can be combined in different ways, taking advantage of each one to find most effective solutions. Choosing the appropriate combination of scalarization techniques and optimization methods depends on the specific nature of the management problem (e.g., if it has a linear or a non-linear relationship), the number of optimization objectives and the constraints involved, complexity of the problem, the availability of computational resources, the need for convergence towards optimal or just approximate solutions, among others (Jain & Singh, 2003; Loucks & van Beek, 2017).

The following sections refer to the most recent developed optimization techniques suitable for solving both single and multi-objective problems. Unlike the methods mentioned previously, these are often based on iterative search metaheuristic approaches that do not require input from decision-makers (like many scalarization techniques), however, there may exist some which may include parameters related to a priori or a posteriori preference.

3.2.3. Multi-objective population-based algorithms

Multi-objective population-based algorithms are techniques that manipulate and transform a set of randomly generated search agents (or initial population) during the optimization process, in order to collectively approximate the Pareto front. These methods are based on probabilistic approaches (Emmerich & Deutz, 2018). These techniques allow an improvement in diversity of the whole search space (Sharma & Kumar, 2022), and can be broadly divided into evolutionary computation and swarm intelligence (Kumar & Yadav, 2022).

3.2.3.1. Multi-objective evolutionary algorithms

Evolutionary Algorithms (EA) were first designed in the 1950s to solve single-optimization problems. In the 1990s, with the evolution of hardware, they showed impressive power in solving highly complex real problems. However, it was after the publication of the first book dedicated exclusively to EA (Deb, 2001), that the number of methods and case studies grew rapidly, becoming an important and promising field of research until today.

They are probabilistic search procedures, which use specific information from the domain of a problem and its objective function to create an initial population of randomly

selected decision vectors. The optimization uses metaheuristic operations based on paradigms from natural selection and biological evolution, such as selection, recombination, and mutation, in an iterative process, towards optimal or near-optimal solutions (Zatarain Salazar et al., 2016; Emmerich & Deutz, 2018; Mirjalili, 2019).

The use of EA within optimization methods helps to maintain precision and convergence of a problem's solution, determine values of performance measures, besides reducing computational effort and processing time. They are very flexible to adapt to each problem, without the need to explicitly indicate the steps to reach the solution (Loucks & van Beek, 2017). However, using these methods cannot guarantee the optimal solution to a problem, but rather an approximate solution which are often sufficient for decision-makers, besides they should be judged qualitatively by an expert (Yang, 2021).

Evolutionary algorithms can be divided into three major groups: Genetic Algorithms (GA), Genetic Programming (GP), and Evolutionary Strategies (ES), being GA the most robust and most common among them for water resources optimization (John et al., 2010). Evolutionary Strategies are often used in conjunction with other EA, as an approach to adapt the parameters of existing algorithms for improving their performances. Genetic Programming is one of the many machine-learning methods mostly used as model building tool to solve specific tasks (Loucks & van Beek, 2017).

The basis of GA is the encoding process of parameters and decision variables into structures called *strings*, which are formed by *bits* whose values usually are in the form of binary arrays (0 or 1), although numbers of any base may be used (Mirjalili, 2019). If compared to genetics, each string would represent a chromosome, and each bit a gene. Therefore, parameters and decision variables are not handled themselves directly by GA, but rather each bit and string represent each characteristic of the problem (Yang, 2021). Figure 15 shows a schematic representation of crossover and mutation operations at a random location in the string in genetic algorithms.

Figure 15 Schematic representation of (left) crossover and (right) mutation at a random location in genetic algorithms - adopted from Yang (2021).

The steps of GA can be basically described as shown in Figure 16.

Data: Objective functions $f(\mathbf{x})$
Result: Best or optimal solution

- 1 Initialize the probabilities of crossover (p_c) and mutation (p_m);
- 2 Encode the solutions into chromosomes (strings);
- 3 Define fitness F (e.g., $F \propto f(\mathbf{x})$ for maximization);
- 4 **while** $t < \text{Max number of generations}$ **do**
- 5 Generate new solution by crossover and mutation;
- 6 Crossover with a crossover probability p_c ;
- 7 Mutate with a mutation probability p_m ;
- 8 Accept the new solutions if their fitness increase;
- 9 Select the current best for the next generation (elitism);
- 10 Update $t = t + 1$;
- 11 **end**
- 12 Decode the results and visualization;

Figure 16 Pseudo-code of a genetic algorithm (Yang, 2021).

According to Reddy & Henze (2023), constrained problems should be reframed into unconstrained ones, and continuous variables should be converted into binary variables by discretizing its range of variability and quantizing them. Yang (2021) points out that the probabilities of crossover and mutation should be carefully chosen as they may strongly affect the search procedures and final solutions. Then, after encoding the objectives and variables, one should define a fitness function or selection criterion to be minimized or maximized, so the initial population of decision vectors can be evaluated, and those with best objective or fitness values are retained. Successive iterations should form different generations by either combining two or more fit individuals using the crossover or mutation operations, then replacing the old population for fitter solutions until a condition (e.g., number of iterations) is met (Mirjalili, 2019).

Since EAs are population-based algorithms, i.e., each solution is transformed simultaneously during the optimization process, a diverse set of search agents can explore the solution space to find multiple Pareto-optimal solutions in one single simulation run (Deb et al., 2002). Thus, it is possible to turn it into a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm (MOEA), however, some adjustments are required as the selection schemes of such algorithms differ from those used in single-objective optimization (Emmerich & Deutz, 2018).

Among the existing paradigms for MOEA designs, the Dominance-based, Indicator-based and Decomposition-based approaches stand out (Emmerich & Deutz, 2018; Sharma & Kumar, 2022), see Figure 11. Each of these approaches adopt different fitness functions to evaluate and guide the selection of the fittest solutions. Besides, penalty functions can be considered to handle different constraints as they usually penalize unsuitable solutions.

The Dominance-based algorithms use a two-level ranking scheme to select fittest solutions, being the first one the dominance relationship among candidate solutions, which is determined by comparing the objective values of each candidate solution, i.e.,

the fitness function assigns a higher fitness value to solutions that are less dominated by other solutions in the population. If they have the same dominance level, a criterion related to diversity (e.g., the crowding distance between solutions) would be evaluated as the second level ranking.

Indicator-based MOEAs are guided by an indicator that measures the performance of a solution set to determine the selection procedure. A popular one is the hypervolume indicator, which gives higher values to solutions as they approximate the true Pareto front.

Finally, the Decomposition-based MOEAs attempt to decompose the problem into several subproblems and each of them would be optimized using different parametrization criteria and scalarization methods to reach a different part of the Pareto front. Each subproblem represents a different trade-off between the original objectives, and the fitness of a solution is determined by its performance on these subproblems.

The non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA) proposed by Srinivas & Deb (1994) was one of the first dominance-based MOEAs. However, the second version (NSGA-II) released by Deb et al. (2002) became much more popular and is still one of the most used algorithms for optimization in water resources (Hadka et al., 2012; Reed et al., 2013; Kumar & Yadav, 2022).

According to Deb et al. (2002), the algorithm starts by initializing a population of candidate solutions randomly. Each solution's fitness is then evaluated and ranked based on its performance across all objective functions. The initial population undergoes recombination (crossover) and mutation to produce offspring solutions, and both are merged. The algorithm selects the half-fittest solutions based on their non-dominance ranking and solution density measured by the crowding distance. This parameter helps NSGA-II maintain the diversity of solutions as it prioritizes the selection of solutions that are in less densely populated areas. This process continues iteratively until a stopping criterion is met, such as a maximum number of generations or convergence.

Figure 17 shows a Pseudo-code of NSGA-II.

Require: Parameters, Initial Population of size N , Maximum Generations

- 1: Set the generation count $i = 0$
- 2: Assess the fitness values of the P_0 population and rank them accordingly.
- 3: **while** $i \leq$ Maximum number of Generations **do**
- 4: Use crossover and mutation to produce an offspring population Q_i of size N .
- 5: Merge parent and offspring populations $R_i \leftarrow P_i \cup Q_i$
- 6: Sort R_i and identify different pareto fronts
- 7: Keep elite members in S_i with size N .
- 8: Calculate crowding distance between the solutions of S_i .
- 9: Perform selection on S_i and update population P_{i+1} .
- 10: Increment the generation count, $i++$.
- 11: **end while**
- 12: Return Population P_{i+1} .

Figure 17 Pseudo-code of NSGA-II (Sharma & Kumar, 2022).

According to Reed et al. (2013), NSGA-II was the primary technological breakthrough that transitioned MOEAs into wide application by adding elitism, efficient non-domination sorting, and parameter-free diversity maintenance. NSGA-II can achieve near optimal solutions well distributed across the Pareto front in a reasonable time, however, poor performance may happen under multiple objectives (more than 3) if the crowding distance function fails (Cho et al., 2017; Ma et al., 2023). It is not necessary to input weight vectors to guide search procedures, but it is essential to know well how to encode the characteristics of the problem and define specific parameters, such as crossover and mutation probabilities. Although it was initially proposed for 2–3 objectives, there are variants that can solve many objectives problems (MaOP) (Sharma & Kumar, 2022). Nevertheless, such improvements were obtained at the cost of diversity (Chakraborty et al., 2019). Ma et al. (2023) highlight that a lot of practical MaOP can often be reduced by identifying and eliminating redundant objectives, which enables existing MOEA to handle such problems well.

Regarding water resources applications, Lewis & Randall (2017) applied the NSGA-II to improve the efficiency of a modelling system previously based on goal programming that used a weighted sum of objectives. They applied it to find the fittest crop selection across dry, average and wet years in the Murrumbidgee Irrigation Area in Australia, to maximize net revenues and minimize environmental flow deficits. They realized that NSGA-II can find the trade-off solutions rapidly, easily and automatically, in contrast to single-objective goal programming solution methods previously used. J. Tian et al. (2019a) used NSGA-II to maximize the economic interest while minimizing the amount of organic pollutants, in addition to Sperner’s lemma approach for fair water resource allocation, in the Hanjiang river basin in China. Tayebikhorami et al. (2019a) used the same algorithm to minimize the difference between water demand and allocated treated wastewater, while minimizing the cost of transferring water between suppliers and users, in four regions of Tehran province, Iran. Naghdi et al. (2021a) applied a simulation-optimization technique using NSGA-II, in addition to a conflict resolution method (Nash bargaining

theory), for optimal allocations of surface water and groundwater among drinking, industrial, agricultural, and environmental sectors, in the Najaf-Abad sub-basin in Iran.

Another Dominance-based MOEA is the Differential Evolution for Multi-objective Optimization (DEMO). It is a vector-based, derivative-free, and population-based method. Unlike genetic algorithms, DEMO operates primarily on vectors and utilizes explicit updating equation, conducting operations on each component of the solution vector, such as the difference between randomly selected vectors for perturbation and vector-based crossover for computational efficiency. It is simple to implement as it does not require encoding and decoding of variables like the binary system adopted in GA. Instead, it uses real numbers to represent design parameters, facilitating a direct search approach. However, it still needs some parameters such as the differential weight and the crossover probability to control the search efficiency. Its advantages lie in its simplicity, ease of use, speed, and robustness (Robič & Filipič, 2005; Yang, 2021; Kumar & Yadav, 2022). According to Emmerich & Deutz (2018), DEMO has improved efficiency and provided more precise results in particular for continuous problems. Other variants of multi-objective differential evolution algorithms can be found in Santana-Quintero & Coello (2005) and in Gong et al. (2009).

In respect to the indicator-based MOEAs, the S-Metric-Selection Evolutionary Multi-Objective Optimization Algorithm (SMS-EMOA) uses a scalar indicator to measure the quality of the Pareto front approximation, which is called hypervolume indicator (Emmerich & Deutz, 2018). This indicator measures the size of the space that is dominated by a set of solutions, which is bound from above by a reference point. Its maximization yields a set of solutions well distributed across the Pareto front, i.e., points move to the Pareto front, and the more they distribute along the Pareto front, the more space gets dominated, thus a larger hypervolume value.

The Hypervolume Estimation Algorithm (HypE) is also an indicator-based MOEA developed by Bader & Zitzler (2011), which can handle high number of objective functions (many-objective optimization problems), using a Monte Carlo Estimation for the hypervolume indicator. There are other indicator-based variants such as the R2 indicator (Trautmann et al., 2013), which attempt to fix computational complexity problems common in indicator-based MOEAs; and the MO-CMA-ES (Igel et al., 2007), which uses an Evolutionary Strategy called Covariance Matrix Adaptation to adapt its mutation distribution and scaling of the objective functions.

Sharma & Kumar (2022) explain that the indicator-based MOEAs have been used primarily because they allow implicit inclusion of user preferences in the optimization process, as well as a measure of the quality of Pareto front approximations to determine the consistency of a Pareto-optimal set. However, user preferences can lead to relatively poor robustness for different classes of problems (Ma et al., 2023), and they could be inefficient in terms of computational complexity as the estimation time increases exponentially with the solution dimension and the number of objectives.

The last group of MOEA to be discussed in this literature review is the decomposition-based algorithms. They divide a multi-objective problem into subproblems using decomposition and scalarization methods based on weights vectors and simultaneously optimize them to reach different parts of the Pareto front (Emmerich & Deutz, 2018). They dynamically assign reference points to subproblems and exchange information by exploring neighbourhood relationships during optimization, thus enhancing search efficiency. According to Y. Xu et al. (2019a), the use of decomposition methods has some advantages in comparison to dominance and indicator-based algorithms, such as they can enhance population diversity, allowing parallelism, and speeding up the solution.

Chakraborty et al. (2019) explain that the main advantage of using scalarization methods in EA, such as aggregation-based methods, is that they can solve MaOP efficiently with minimal change when conducting the selection of solutions. However, it is important to understand how weights have been defined and how to update the best-known solution for objectives. Moreover, none of such methods has been recognized so far as a universally accepted method.

MOEA/D (Zhang & Li, 2007) is a relevant algorithm in this group since it has established itself as a benchmark for new MOEAs by winning the 2009 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (Reed et al., 2013), and in recent years it has received more coverage (Emmerich & Deutz, 2018). It simplifies complexity by leveraging interactions within a single population, in addition to combining Pareto dominance with decomposition techniques, facilitating the use of hybrid algorithms for improved results. Although MOEA/D can handle MaOP solving all subproblems simultaneously, it requires additional parameters if compared to other MOEAs (like NSGA-II), such as predefined set of weight vectors used to maintain the solution diversity (Ma et al., 2023).

Decomposition-based algorithms are often used to develop hybrid algorithms to get better results (Sharma & Kumar, 2022). The main research directions have been focusing on improving weight vector generation and mating selection, as well as new decomposition methods and replacement procedures. Some variants of MOEA/D can be checked on the following references: K. Li et al. (2014); Mashwani et al. (2016); de Farias & Araújo (2022); and Zhao et al. (2022).

NSGA-III (Deb & Jain, 2014) is another decomposition-based algorithm specially designed for unconstrained MaOP, which uses the basic framework of NSGA-II, although it also uses a well-spread set of reference point to maintain diversity of solution in the Pareto front, which is dynamically updated in its decomposition process (Sharma & Kumar, 2022). Hence, instead of adopting the crowding distance used in NSGA-II to select non-dominated solutions, NSGA-III uses another selection operator based on reference points to choose non-dominated solutions (Ma et al., 2023). Deb & Jain (2014) explain that reference points can either be predefined in a structured manner or supplied preferentially by the user, allowing this method to be used in a combined application of decision-making and many-objective optimization.

The NSGA-III does not require any additional parameter to be set, unlike other MOEAs (such as MOEA/D), and solve convex, concave, disjointed, differently scaled, and multimodal MOP (Deb & Jain, 2014). Furthermore, it has uniform diversity (Sharma & Kumar, 2022). Ma et al. (2023) point out that although NSGA-III has no obvious advantage in comparison to NSGA-II for MOP with two or three objectives, it can handle MaOP (up to 15 objectives) unlike the older version. However, NSGA-III may also have weaknesses, such as decision-making difficulty, evaluations of diversity measures and performance metrics are computationally expensive, and it may depend on predefined reference points provided by experts to select solutions. Sharma & Kumar (2022) also alert that computational complexity increases with the number of reference points and it may handle constraints inefficiently.

NSGA-III is being updated and improved, especially in water resources applications, as are the metaheuristic-based algorithms mentioned in this section. C. Chen et al. (2017) proposed an improved non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm-III called ENSGA-III for solving reservoir flood control operations. They adapted the initial population generation to get a more spread and uniform population in the search space, in addition to the ϵ -dominance mechanism, constraint violation and three-archive strategies, which enabled better performance for this type of problem in terms of uniformity and diversity distribution. Janus et al. (2023) integrated a spatially distributed and physically-based hydrologic model with a network-based multi-sector water resources management model, which used NSGA-III for the optimization. Their goal was to identify land cover patterns that optimize trade-offs between water, food, energy and environment objectives. They successfully combined promising tools and software packages in a complex framework, such as Platypus, ParFlow/CLM model, and Pywr library, and reached real benefits of coupling simulation and optimization models.

Ma et al. (2023) provided Table 1 with important websites and source codes of NSGA variants, which may be useful for anyone interested in studying further this subject.

Table 1 Websites and source codes of NSGA-II and NSGA-III and their variants - adopted from Ma et al. (2023).

Description	Links
NSGA-II Python version	https://github.com/baopng/NSGA-II
NSGA-II MATLAB version	https://es.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/10429-nsga-ii-a-multi-objective-optimization-algorithm
NSGA-III Python version	https://github.com/lmarti/nsgaiii
NSGA-III MATLAB version	https://es.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/60678-nsga-iii-in-matlab
All code set	https://github.com/topics/nsga3

Description	Links
GUI visual tool (PlatEMO)	https://github.com/BIMK/PlatEMO

There are several studies regarding comparison among metaheuristics optimization techniques. Zatarain Salazar et al. (2016) performed a comparative study to evaluate the use of an Evolutionary Multi-Objective Direct Policy Search (EMODPS), and different kinds of MOEAs to discover the Pareto approximate operating policies from Conowingo reservoirs, in Pennsylvania, USA. They have assessed ϵ -MOEA, ϵ -NSGAI, Borg MOEA, NSGA-II, GDE3 (a relevant differential evolution algorithm for MOP), OMOPSO, and MOEA/D. They concluded that the ϵ -MOEA, the auto-adaptive Borg MOEA, and ϵ -NSGAI yielded superior results for the proposed six-objective optimization problem. This study also confirms other recent MOEA diagnostics (Hadka et al., 2012; Reed et al., 2013; Ward et al., 2015) indicating that the Borg MOEA is a promising technique and has performed consistently well across a wider water applications suite. Borg MOEA is not just an algorithm, but a hyper-heuristic framework that assimilated several important design principles from existing MOEAs, which is composed of auto-adaptive search operators based on the optimization progress, contributing to maintaining diversity and facilitating escape from local optima, besides enhancing the search for complex MaOP, and can be easily extended for use on parallel computing.

Nevertheless, Emmerich & Deutz (2018) highlight that it is not easy to choose the right method and that it often depends mainly on the dimension of the objective space, i.e., how many objective functions, the number and distribution of desired solutions, and if there is previous knowledge on the location and shape of the Pareto front. Furthermore, Y. Tian, Si, et al. (2021) alert that the majority of MOEAs were usually developed for solving small-scale multi-objective optimization problems, which are inefficient for solving large-scale multi-objective optimization problems (LSMOPs) with very high-dimensional decision spaces.

Finally, Figure 18 shows a table of relevant multi-objective optimization software, taken from Emmerich & Deutz (2018). For clarity, EMO means evolutionary multi-objective or multi-criterion optimization, EA evolutionary algorithm, and MOO multi-objective optimization.

Table 1 Table of (evolutionary) multiobjective optimization software

Libraries (evolutionary) multiobjective optimization			
Name	Scope	Prog. Lang.	url or ref
<i>Public domain</i>			
ecr	EA and EMO	R	Bossek (2017)
JMetal	Metatheuristics/EMO	Java	Barba-González et al. (2017)
Liger	MOO/Design Optim.	C++	Giagkiozis et al. (2013)
MOEA framework	EMO	Java	moeaframework.org/
Opt4J	EMO	Java	opt4j.sourceforge.net
PISA	EMO	C++	Bleuler et al. (2003)
PyMOO	EMO	Python	www.openhub.net/p/pymoo
RODEOlib	Robust Optimization	Matlab	sourceforge.net/projects/rodeo/lib/
Shark Library	Machine Learning	C#	image.diku.dk/shark/
SUMO	Bayesian Optimization	Matlab	sumo.intec.ugent.be/SUMO
TEA	classical EA and MOO	C++	Emmerich and Hosenberg (2000)
vOptSolver	(Linear) MOO	Julia	voptsolver.github.io/vOptSolver
<i>Commercial software</i>			
EASY	Design Optimization	C++	velos0.ltt.mech.ntua.gr/EASY/
IND-NIMBUS	Design Optimization	N/A	ind-nimbus.it.jyu.fi
ISight	Design Optimization	N/A	www.simuleon.com
MODEfrontier	Design Optimization	N/A	www.esteco.com
Optimus	Design Optimization	N/A	www.noessolutions.com
WWW-NIMBUS	Design Optimization	N/A	Miettinen and Mäkelä (2000)
<i>Performance assessment</i>			
Performance assessment test problems			
BBOB/COCO	Benchmarking Tool	C++	coco.gforge.inria.fr/
WFG	Test Suite	C++	www.wfg.csse.uwa.edu.au/toolkit/
ZDT/DTLZ	Test Suite	C++	esa.github.io/pagmo2/
Performance assessment software			
Attainment surfaces		R/C	lopez-ibanez.eu/eaftools
Hypervolume computation		C	lopez-ibanez.eu/hypervolume
Hypervolume computation	Link Collection	Various	ls11-www.cs.tu-dortmund.de/rudolph/hypervolume/start

Figure 18 Evolutionary multi-objective optimization software (Emmerich & Deutz, 2018).

3.2.3.2. Multi-objective swarm-based algorithms

Swarm Intelligence (SI) was first introduced in 1989 as an intelligent multiagent system that simulates the behaviour of social insects, such as ants and bees, and swarms, such as a flock of birds. Just like EA, swarm-based algorithms (SbA) are also iterative population-based techniques, however, the performance of SI is optimized by adapting to the environment instead of competing among themselves (Kumar & Yadav, 2022). Sharma & Kumar (2022) explain that SbA uses an individual's prior experiences and interactions in their neighbourhood or social context to evolve in a decentralized way, i.e., they take advantage of local-level interactions to achieve global-level responses.

There are lots of swarm-based optimization algorithms. However, the most used SbA for multi-objective optimization are Multi-Objective Particle Swarm Optimization (MOPSO), Multi-Objective Ant Colony Optimization (MOACO), Multi-Objective Cuckoo Search (MOCS), and Multi-Objective Firefly Algorithm (MOFA), to mention a few (Yang, 2021; Sharma & Kumar, 2022). MOPSO and their variants (also hybrid algorithms) are the most common among them in water resources applications (M & G, 2008; Jahandideh-Tehrani et al., 2020; Janga Reddy & Nagesh Kumar, 2020). Section 3.5 gives some references about MOPSO applications in water resources.

PSO (Eberhart & Kennedy, 1995) is inspired by the swarm intelligence of fish and birds and simulates a swarm of particles or multiple agents that start searching an unknown destination (fitness function) from some initial random guess and take advantage of their own experience and neighbour information to reach their best common goal (global solutions).

The algorithm starts with an initial random position and associated velocity for each particle in the search space. The direction and magnitude of the velocity vectors are adjusted in each iteration (or generation) based on stochastic vectors and deterministic components, such as acceleration constants and inertia components. Each particle is attracted toward the current best global position (with the largest fitness value) and its own best location that is registered in its memory, while at the same time, it tends to move randomly. After moving all particles, the fitness value of each particle is calculated, and its best position, as well as the best global position, is updated. This process continues for a fixed number of iterations or until a stopping criterion is reached (Reyes-Sierra & Coello, 2006; Janga Reddy & Nagesh Kumar, 2007; Wang et al., 2018; Trivedi et al., 2020).

Figure 19 shows the general flowchart of the particle swarm optimization algorithm.

Figure 19 General flowchart of the particle swarm optimization algorithm (D. Wang et al., 2018).

Multi-Objective Particle Swarm Optimization (MOPSO) was firstly proposed by Coello & Lechuga (2002), since then a large number of MOPSO variants were developed (Trivedi et al., 2020). Reyes-Sierra & Coello (2006) proposed an Optimized Multi-objective Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm (OMOPSO), which improved its performance by incorporating the epsilon dominance and crowding factors maintaining convergence and diversity. G. Xu et al. (2019) proposed a multi-objective sorting-based learning (MSL) strategy for PSO, which improved its performance by simultaneously considering better fitness value and diversity instead of global best individual as general MOPSO does. They achieved a better balance between exploration and exploitation, and better performance in terms of solution quality, convergence speed and algorithm reliability. Yang et al. (2020) developed a Many-Objective Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm (CMaPSO) based on competition mechanism. It was compared with other MOPSOs variants and MOEAs designed to solve MaOP, and it had superior performance with better convergence and diversity.

Trivedi et al. (2020), Janga Reddy & Nagesh Kumar (2020) and Kumar & Yadav (2022) give many other examples of PSO variants and their applications, especially regarding water resources management, whereas D. Wang et al. (2018) present a complete description about PSO origin and background, structure of the algorithm and related concepts to whom wants to delve in this subject.

Yang (2021) points out that PSO has become one of the most widely used SI-based algorithms due to its simplicity and flexibility, as it does not need encoding or decoding of the parameters into binary strings, but real-number strings can also be used. Reddy & Henze (2023), Kumar & Yadav (2022), and Sharma & Kumar (2022) agree that it is powerful for solving multi-objective, non-linear, multimodal, and complex problems with fast convergence and low computational costs. Nevertheless, the same authors think that the dependency of tuning parameters such as inertia weights or social, and cognitive parameters could be a drawback. Besides, according to Zatarain Salazar et al. (2016), OMOPSO had inferior performance than other MOEAs (such as ϵ -NSGA-II and ϵ -MOEA), and Sharma & Kumar (2022) concluded that MOPSO variants usually are worse at finding Pareto solutions than evolutionary algorithms.

3.3. Simulation – optimization modeling

Previous sections referred only to optimization techniques; however, they should be combined with simulation models. This section gives some insights, tools, and strategies for the simulation-optimization approach.

According to Loucks & van Beek (2017), the simulation-optimization modelling approach is one of the main and most effective ways of evaluating system designs and operational policies. Optimization should be used as a preliminary screening tool to find a reasonable number of solutions and alternatives to the problem, which are further evaluated and improved by accurate simulations of the system. Borden et al. (2016) explained that

simulation software packages are usually more flexible as they are not as constrained with assumptions as optimization approaches, and they address “what-if” scenarios, i.e., what will likely happen at locations throughout the domain under varied conditions.

This type of approach serves as an important tool for Decision Support Systems (DSS), helping managers to make real-time decisions in reservoir and flood controlling, irrigation system management, and water allocation, in addition to enabling taking hydrological uncertainty into account when finding optimal solutions to water resource planning problems.

Figure 20 shows an example flowchart of a simulation-optimization modelling approach.

Figure 20 Coupling the simulation and optimization models (Karimanzira, 2016).

Karimanzira (2016) point out that the simulation-optimization approach is usually divided into two parts that comprise the Decision Support System (DSS). In the first part, complex and detailed models to simulate surface water and groundwater are developed to represent the real system conditions. The second part should support a search process for the most attractive decision option, where possible strategies involving stakeholders’ interests and desired attributes of the water resource management system are evaluated. This second part of the DSS framework is usually composed of a coupled simulation-optimization model, in which the simulation model should be simpler and reduced to have fewer parameters than in the first part, and avoid high computational effort; then, the alternatives can be verified more dynamically. Once suitable results are obtained, they should be verified using a more detailed simulation model. The authors highlight that it is a dynamic process with data input, analysis, and decision-making in an almost continuous way.

Derepasko et al. (2021) defined two major phases for the optimization process (Figure 21), the first one is identifying or understanding the management problem to be solved, in which the spatial and temporal characterization of all system components are carried out. They also think the stakeholders' interests and all existing conflicts should be mapped during this system characterization phase, as well as the main objectives and constraints acknowledged. Once the overall context has been understood, the second phase includes the entire process of mathematically representing the problem in objective and constraint functions and defining the most appropriate optimization methods and scenarios.

Figure 21 General optimization steps (Derepasko et al., 2021).

This approach can be applied in several water resource problems. Iman et al. (2021) applied an integrated simulation-optimization framework, in which a detailed simulation model of the system was developed in WEAP, which was linked to NSGA-II with the aid of WEAP application programming interface (API). They aimed at the optimal conjunctive use of surface and groundwater in the Zayandehrud river basin in Iran, considering the operational reservoir parameters, water allocation for agricultural lands, and withdrawals from the river and groundwater sources, as decision variables for the optimization process. The first objective function was to minimize the ratio of the sum of the supply deficit to the average monthly demand of 11 agricultural regions, which was written as

$$\text{Min}(\text{Deficit}) = \text{Min} \left[\sum_{y=1}^5 \sum_{m=1}^{12} \sum_{j=1}^{11} \left(\frac{D_{m,y}^j - \text{SUP}_{m,y}^j}{D_{ave,y}^j} \right) \right] \quad (7)$$

where y is the number of the year; m is the number of the month; and j is the number of the irrigation region. The $D_{m,y}^j$ is the irrigation demand for each region, month, and year. $\text{SUP}_{m,y}^j$ is the sum of surface water and groundwater supplied from the canal and

aquifer respectively. $D_{ave,y}^j$ is the monthly average irrigation demand for each region and each year.

The second objective function was to maximize a fuzzy sustainability index of water resources in the basin, which was written as

$$\text{Max (Sustainability of Water Resources)} = \text{Max}[SG = \sum W^R \times SI^R] \quad (8)$$

where, W^R is the weight for each water resource and SI^R is a sustainability index subject to some constraints, such as the continuity equation for the reservoir and aquifers, evaporation losses for the reservoir, and the capacity limits of each canal.

After generating a random initial population of decision variables in MOEA, the network linear programming from WEAP was used to optimize the values of water allocations to irrigation regions according to the constraints and the parameters for reservoir operation. Then, WEAP simulates the interactions between surface water and groundwater, which generates new values of water allocations and storage volumes of the reservoir and aquifers, which, again, serve as input to NSGA-II for optimization. This iterative process enabled the identification of policies that provided an optimal trade-off between the two objectives, clearly better than a previous simulation model conducted alone.

Janus et al. (2023) took advantage of a simulation-optimization framework to identify the fittest land cover patterns in their study area by integrating a spatially distributed and physically based hydrologic model into the optimization algorithm NSGA-III. It was implemented in a framework for evolutionary computing in Python, called Platypus, in addition to a groundwater flow simulator ParFlow, coupled with a land surface model CLM, and a water resource modelling library, Pywr.

The framework is basically described as follows. Firstly, runoff time-series are extracted from ParFlow/CLM model outputs, which are executed in Pywr to obtain state variables. The outputs and state variables are then used to formulate objective functions for the MOEA, which sets the configuration of land covers that serves as input to ParFlow/CLM model again. The study confirmed the benefits of coupling distributed hydrologic models with water management simulation for multisector multicriteria land cover planning.

In fact, there are a lot of study cases that use simulation-optimization approaches to evaluate system designs and operational policies in water resources applications. These are some other references to interested readers: Singh, 2014; Norouzi Khatiri et al., 2020; Jiang et al., 2021; Kerebih & Keshari, 2021; Cai et al., 2022.

There are specialized software packages aimed at integrating hydrological models and optimization, such as **Aquatool** (decision support system for watershed planning and management or water resource); **WEAP** (water evaluation and planning system); **MIKE SHE** (semi-distributed hydrological Model), **MODSIM** (modelling and simulation), among others.

Borden et al. (2016) presented several of the main software packages used to simulate hydrological processes, some of which also consider optimisation at some point in the modelling process (Figure 22).

Software Developer	Software Package	Water Resources Applications											
		Rainfall-Runoff	Water Allocation	River Flows Routing	General Hydrology*	Reservoir Operations	Irrigation	Flood Mapping	Flood Warning	Groundwater**	Conjunctive Use	Water Quality	Sediment Transport
Aquaveo	GMS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	X	-
CSU	MODSIM-DSS	-	X	X	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Deltares	Delft3D Suite	X	-	X	-	X	-	X	X	-	-	X	X
Deltares	iMod	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	X	-
Deltares	RIBASIM	X	X	X	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	-
Deltares	SOBEK v2.14	X	X	X	-	X	-	X	X	-	-	X	X
DHI	MIKE I	X	X	X	-	X	-	X	X	-	-	X	X
DHI	MIKE SHE-MIKE I	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	-
DHI	MIKE FLOOD	X	-	X	-	X	-	X	X	-	-	X	X
DHI	MIKE21C	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X
DHI	MIKE HYDRO Basin	X	X	X	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	-
eWater	Source	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	X	-
NIH	ReSyP	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
RockWare	Groundwater Vistas	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	X	-
SEI	WEAP	X	X	X	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	-
USACE	GSSHA(WMS)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	-
USACE	HEC-RAS, HEC-HMS, HEC-RESSIM	X	-	X	-	X	-	X	X	-	-	X	X
USDA	SWAT	X	-	X	X	-	X	-	-	X	X	X	X
USGS	MODFLOW	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	-
USGS	GSFLOW	X	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	-	X	-
USGS	MODFLOW-OWHM	-	X	X	X	-	X	-	-	X	X	X	-
Waterloo Hydrogeologic	Visual MODFLOW	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	X	-

* Simulates the full hydrologic cycle beyond lumped conceptual rainfall-runoff models.
 ** Simulates groundwater movement using physical equations applied to a discretized grid.

Figure 22 Water resource software and their application (Borden et al., 2016).

3.4. Conflict resolution methods

The previous sections referred mainly to the techniques used to find the fittest solutions to multiple conflicting objectives and possible options available for decision-makers, however, choosing the final decision usually has many difficulties. Since water resource management is often a controversial topic among stakeholders, conflict resolution methods have many applications in water allocation debates (Madani & Hipel, 2011; Aljefri et al., 2019), especially in shared groundwater systems (Raquel et al., 2007; Nazari & Ahmadi, 2019).

Cho et al. (2017) explain some conflict resolution methods as game theory-based MOO design techniques. According to them, they are very similar to MOO approaches

described in section 3.2 as both aim to optimize multiple objectives at the same time, however, non-cooperative game theory aims to identify Nash Equilibrium (NE) which may not be the Pareto optimal solutions.

If compared to Pareto Optimality, Nash Equilibrium has a slight difference, and could be described as a state in which no objective can be improved without worsening at least one other objective, however, no objective has an incentive to change its strategy unilaterally. Thus, while optimization methods traditionally focus on maximizing or minimizing objective functions, conflict resolution methods consider a broader range of objectives and interests, and they often emphasize the importance of cooperation and compromise (Nisan et al. 2007).

Naghdi et al. (2021) comment that conflict resolution methods in water resources problems are usually classified into two main categories: analytical methods (e.g., game theory) and quantitative models (e.g., Nash bargaining method). From many case studies analysed in section 3.5, the Nash Bargaining Solution (NBS) (Nash, 1950) is the most used conflict resolution method in water resources management.

According to Nash (1950), a solution should satisfy the following axioms:

- **Pareto Optimality** - no objective can be improved without worsening at least one other objective.
- **Invariant to equivalent utility representations** - The bargaining solution should not depend on how preferences are represented in terms of utility, it must be consistent regardless of how utilities are measured or expressed, ensuring that the solution is robust.
- **Independence of irrelevant alternatives** - options outside the bargain should not affect the distribution of resources in question, meaning that NBS depend only on the stakeholders' preferences and not on any available external alternatives.
- **Symmetry** - All stakeholders must have equal opportunities to influence the outcome of the bargain.

Essentially, the Nash bargaining solution is reached when both sides from a conflicting management problem reach a distribution of resources which no objective can be improved without worsening at least one other objective. The results are considered fair and efficient, as they take into account the preferences and bargaining powers of both stakeholders. NSB is based on the concept of a collective utility function that can be maximized, i.e., the utility function which aggregated utilities of each conflicting individual (stakeholders or different decision-makers), which can be maximized to find the best collective solution (Nisan et al., 2007). The NBS goal can be expressed as (Delpasand et al., 2020)

$$OP = \text{Max.} \prod_{i=1}^s (f_i - d_i)^{w_i}, d_i \leq f_i \quad (9)$$

where OP is an optimal solution in the Pareto front; s is the number of stakeholders or decision-makers, f_i is utility function of the i_{th} stakeholder; d_i is the minimum acceptable utility for the i_{th} stakeholder; and w_i is the relative weight of the i_{th} stakeholder.

As a main advantage, NBS provides a less complex and generic solution strategy for various cooperative bargaining processes. However, it is not straightforward to select and adjust cooperative decisions that reflect unique characteristics of conflicting management problems, besides it is non-trivial to evaluate axioms (Cho et al., 2017).

Naghdi et al. (2021) applied a simulation-optimization technique using NSGA-II, in addition to the NBS method whose main objective was to develop a coupled model using system dynamics, MOEA and conflict resolution for surface water and groundwater resources allocation in an integrated manner. Farhadi et al. (2016a) applied NBS in conjunction with an optimization model and an agent-based model to find a sustainable solution for groundwater management in Daryan Aquifer, Fars Province, Iran. While the NBS model sought solutions based on each stakeholder's preferences, socially influential factors and policy mechanisms were implemented in the agent-based model to encourage agents to cooperate with the management decisions, generating new modified optimum solutions according to social conditions. Hence, they applied NBS again to find a compromise among the modified optimal objectives of the stakeholders.

Interested readers can find a good overview of other existing conflict resolution methods in the study from Cho et al. (2017), such as Nontransferable Utility Game (NTU), Hedonic Game, Vickrey's Auction, Combinatorial Auction, as well as the benefits and disadvantages of using each method, and other references beyond those mentioned in section 3.5.

3.5. Applications in water management

Recognizing water management challenges as scenarios necessitating multi-objective optimization (MOO) is evident. Given the complex interactions among different sectors and stakeholders in IWRM, leveraging MOO proves to be a powerful tool. It empowers decision-makers to tackle numerous conflicting objectives simultaneously.

Once the fundamental concepts and methodologies around MOO have been elucidated in the previous sections, this section pivots towards exploring the realm of MOO applied to water management issues through a literature review. In this review, we aim to identify prevalent approaches in multi-objective and multi-sectoral water management, alongside the tools and datasets utilized in such aim.

To achieve this objective, we utilized a combination of search terms, including "water management," "multi-sectoral," or/and "water resources," along with "multi-objective optimization" and its variations such as "multi-objective optimization," "multi-objective optimization," and "multi-objective optimization." We also included terms like "water storage" and "water distribution systems" in our search queries. These searches were

conducted across various academic databases, including Google Scholar, Thomson ISI Web of Science, Scopus, and ScienceDirect. We limited our search to include papers published from 2014 onward, thereby encompassing the most recent decade to ensure the inclusion of the latest techniques utilized in the field.

Initially, we identified 299 papers in Scopus and ScienceDirect, 70 papers in Google Scholar, and an additional 86 in Web of Science. According to data from the Scopus database, it wasn't until 2010 that articles on these topics began to be increasingly published year after year. Figure 23 illustrates the trend in the number of papers on these subjects found in Scopus since 1992. The pattern observed since 2014 mirrors that seen in the Web of Science and Google Scholar databases. It's worth noting that some papers appeared in multiple databases, which was anticipated and explains the similar trends across platforms.

Figure 23 Evolution of the number of papers found in Scopus since 1992.

After obtaining an initial overview of the number of publications in each database, we evaluated the selected papers to eliminate any duplications between databases. Subsequently, we honed our selection criteria by closely examining the abstracts, specifically targeting studies that showcased a clear application of multi-objective optimization in water management, particularly adopting a multisectoral approach involving at least two sectors. Where feasible, we prioritized studies addressing conjunctive water use. We have also prioritized selecting papers that showcased case study applications, paying particular attention to those that could offer valuable insights into resolving the challenges identified in the demo sites of the OurMED project. Through this rigorous process, we selected 38 papers for detailed investigation.

From the selected papers, we extracted pertinent information including the countries of origin, publication journals, and indexing keywords. Using this data, we compiled a comprehensive overview of publications pertaining to the subject.

Most of the papers originated from Iran (47%), followed closely by China (40%). Papers from the United States of America, the United Kingdom, Turkey, and Saudi Arabia

As previously stated, only studies that encompassed two or more sectors were included. Among these sectors, the majority of papers (80%) focused on the agriculture sector, followed by domestic affairs, industry, the environment, urban development, energy, and tourism.

- **Objective functions**

Most of the papers considered two (50%) (e.g. Safavi et al., 2016; Dou et al., 2019; Tian et al., 2019; Yuan et al., 2022) or three (33%) (e.g. Farhadi et al., 2016; Alizadeh et al., 2017; Naghdi et al., 2021) objective functions and only 17% considered four or more objective functions (AlZahrani et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2023), evidencing the priority to make the optimization problems as simple as possible.

Additionally, upon analysing the types of objectives utilized in optimization tasks, it was found that objectives concerning equity and fairness in water distribution, demand coverage and the prevention of shortages were present in 83% of the papers. These objectives aimed to either maximize the fairness of water distribution, ensure equity in water use, meet supplied demands, or minimize water deficit and shortage (e.g. D. Chen et al., 2016; Farhadi et al., 2016; Alizadeh et al., 2017; M. Chen et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2019; Kazemi et al., 2020; Tang et al., 2021).

In 67% of the papers, researchers integrated at least one function directly associated with economic considerations. These objectives were geared towards either maximizing economic benefits and revenue or minimizing distribution and operational costs (e.g. Habibi Davijani et al., 2016; Tian et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2019; Kazemi et al., 2020; Tang et al., 2021; Yuan et al., 2022).

Objectives directly related to groundwater were identified in 38% of the papers. These objectives predominantly involved minimizing groundwater drawdown and extraction (Nouiri et al., 2015; Farhadi et al., 2016; Heydari et al., 2016; Safavi et al., 2016; Alizadeh et al., 2017; Naghdi et al., 2021; Zeinali et al., 2020).

Water quality objectives were present in 35% of the papers, with a primary focus on minimizing concentrations and discharge of pollutants, total dissolved solids, and salinity (Nouiri et al., 2015; AlZahrani et al., 2016; Tian et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2023).

Environmental objectives were identified in 10% of the papers, primarily focusing on aspects such as guaranteeing an environmental flow (D. Chen et al., 2016; M. Chen et al., 2019; KhazaiPoul et al., 2019; J. Xu & Bai, 2019; Dehghanipour et al., 2020) and the overall sustainability of the system (Aalami et al., 2020; Dong et al., 2022).

Objective functions related to wastewater treatment, wetland preservation, recreational use of water, and energy generation were identified less frequently (D. Chen et al., 2016; M. Chen et al., 2019; Dou et al., 2019; Tayebikhorami et al., 2019).

- **Decision variables**

In our analysis, we have identified that the majority of decision variables are associated with the allocation of water, whether it pertains to the total volume or specific sectors, alongside variables such as pumping rate, crop area allocation, environmental flow, total costs, reservoir or wastewater discharge, and the ratio of superficial to groundwater usage. It's worth noting that while objectives and constraints are consistently delineated in all papers, the discussion around decision variables is often lacking. In OurMED, it is crucial to furnish comprehensive information regarding the optimization process, including the specific decision variables employed for each demo-site to improve the understanding of our tools and their results.

- **Constraints**

We have classified the identified constraints into nine main types as follows:

Capacity constraint: 26% of the identified constraints were related to the capacity. It includes the reservoir volume, level, discharge, and/or outflow, as well as aspects related to water supply and delivery, pump stations, transmission links, or power generation capacity (Nouiri et al., 2015; D. Chen et al., 2016; Li et al., 2018; M. Chen et al., 2019; KhazaiPoul et al., 2019; Tian et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2022; Yuan et al., 2022). For instance, a capacity constraint could be established to ensure that the reservoir volume does not drop below a specified threshold, guaranteeing an adequate water supply during dry periods.

Resources constraint: 24% of the identified constraints were related to the availability of the resources. It includes the number of allocated resources, the maximum allowable pumping and the quantity of wastewater produced (Heydari et al., 2016; Tarebari et al., 2018; Kazemi et al., 2020; Deng et al., 2022; Dong et al., 2022; Yuan et al., 2022). For instance, a resources constraint could be established to limit the maximum pumping rate of an aquifer to prevent excessive depletion and ensure sustainable groundwater management. Additionally, another resources constraint could focus on limiting the amount of water allocated for agricultural irrigation purposes.

Demand constraint: 15% of the identified constraints were related to the limitation of the demands (Abdullah et al., 2018; J. Tian et al., 2019b; Dehghanipour et al., 2020; Guan et al., 2020; Deng et al., 2022; Dong et al., 2022). For example, a demand constraint could be imposed to ensure equitable allocation of water resources among different water use departments within each subregion, based on the Gini efficiency principle. This constraint stipulates that the quantity of water allocated to each department cannot surpass the water requirement quantity of those departments in each subarea, while adhering to principles of fairness and efficiency.

Space and/or time constraint: 10% of the identified constraints were associated with the spatial and/or temporal aspects of various activities or processes (Habibi Davijani et al.,

2016; Heydari et al., 2016; Dou et al., 2019; Yazdian et al., 2021; L. Liu et al., 2023). For instance, this type of constraint dictates that contaminants must not remain in the water within the wetland for an extended period. Alternatively, it might involve setting limits on the maximum land area allocated for planting a specific crop.

Water balance constraint: 6% of the identified constraints were defined as water balance constraints. It ensures that the inflow and outflow of water within a system are balanced, maintaining the integrity and sustainability of water resources (D. Chen et al., 2016; M. Chen et al., 2019; KhazaiPoul et al., 2019; Tian et al., 2019; Deng et al., 2022;). For instance, it could stipulate that the total inflow of water in a reservoir, comprising precipitation, runoff from surrounding catchment areas, and upstream tributary flows, must be equal to the total outflow, which includes water released for downstream users, evaporation losses, and seepage.

Nonnegative constraint: 6% of the identified constraints were defined as nonnegative constraints ensuring that the decision variables maintain nonnegative values, meaning they cannot be less than zero (AlZahrani et al., 2016; Tian et al., 2019; Z. Wang et al., 2022). For instance, in water allocation, this constraint dictates that the amount of water allocated to any specific entity or purpose should be greater than or equal to zero. While applicable to capacity, demand, or resource constraints, this constraint holds particular significance in maintaining water balance, where inflow and outflow in reservoirs or water distribution systems must be balanced, as mentioned above.

Environmental constraint: 5% of the identified constraints were defined as environmental constraints and it includes limitations related to the environmental demand (J. Tian et al., 2019b; Kazemi et al., 2020; Tang et al., 2021; Yuan et al., 2022). For instance, ensuring that the ecological water use exceeds the minimum regional ecological water demand.

Quality constraint: 4% of the identified constraints were related to quality including limitation of pollutant concentrations and salinity levels (AlZahrani et al., 2016; Dou et al., 2019; Norouzi Khatiri et al., 2020). For instance, one quality constraint involves the treatment intensity of sewage outlets, where the concentration of pollutants must be controlled within a specified range.

Economic constraint: 3% of the identified constraints were related to economic aspects, including the limitation of the costs, and a minimum or a maximum profit (AlZahrani et al., 2016; Habibi Davijani et al., 2016; Tarebari et al., 2018; Dehghanipour et al., 2020). For instance, one economic constraint could involve establishing a minimum agricultural profit requirement to ensure that the proposed crop pattern generates at least the same agricultural profit as the current crop pattern. Additionally, another economic constraint could focus on minimizing the net cost of water allocation across the entire subbasin area. This ensures efficient resource utilization while considering economic factors.

- **Optimization algorithms**

A We have identified that in 15% of the selected papers, multiple optimization algorithms were utilized for comparison or complementary purposes (D. Chen et al., 2016; M. Chen et al., 2019; J. Xu & Bai, 2019; Tang et al., 2021).

The nondominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA) was a prominent choice, utilized in 74% of the selected papers, either alone or in combination with other methods. Among these, 56% employed NSGAI (Heydari et al., 2016; Alizadeh et al., 2017; Tayebikhorami et al., 2019b; J. Tian et al., 2019b; J. Xu & Bai, 2019; Zeinali et al., 2020; Goorani & Shabanlou, 2021; Deng et al., 2022; L. Liu et al., 2023), while 18% utilized a modified version of NSGAI (Nouiri et al., 2015; D. Chen et al., 2016; M. Chen et al., 2019; Tang et al., 2021).

The particle swarm optimization (PSO) and its variations were used in 21% of the selected papers (Habibi Davijani et al., 2016; M. Chen et al., 2019; Dehghanipour et al., 2020; ; Norouzi Khatiri et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022; Yuan et al., 2022). Additionally, 15% of the selected papers utilized both NSGA and PSO methods to compare their performance (Habibi Davijani et al., 2016; M. Chen et al., 2019; Tang et al., 2021).

Other methods were used in 21% of the selected papers, either alone or in combination with NSGA method (W. K. Li et al., 2018; Tarebari et al., 2018; Dou et al., 2019; J. Xu & Bai, 2019).

- **Tools**

We have identified that the tools utilized in the selected papers are diverse, and their usage can vary depending on the available data, objectives, and tool availability. Groundwater flow and contaminant transport were simulated with MODFLOW and MT3D, respectively (Heydari et al., 2016; Farhadi et al., 2016; Alizadeh et al., 2017; Dehghanipour et al., 2020; Norouzi Khatiri et al., 2020; Zeinali et al., 2020; Yazdian et al., 2021; Far & Ashofteh, 2024).

Surface water resources were simulated employing WEAP (KhazaiPoul et al., 2019; Dehghanipour et al., 2020; Kazemi et al., 2020; Zeinali et al., 2020; Goorani & Shabanlou, 2021), SWAT (KhazaiPoul et al., 2019), MIKE (Dou et al., 2019), CatchWatSD (Liu et al., 2023, and Delft3D (Abdullah et al., 2018).

Additionally, several papers focused their analysis on data or empirical models from the field of hydrology (Xevi & Khan, 2005; AlZahrani et al., 2016; Li et al., 2018; Tarebari et al., 2018; M. Chen et al., 2019; Guan et al., 2020; Deng et al., 2022; Dong et al., 2022; Z. Wang et al., 2022). System dynamics approach was also employed in some papers (Naghdi et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2021).

Artificial neural networks (ANN) were employed as surrogate models in several papers (Farhadi et al., 2016b; Heydari et al., 2016; Safavi et al., 2016; Yazdian et al., 2021). This acknowledgment underscores the importance of recognizing and addressing uncertainties inherent in water resources research.

Finally, it is important to mention that given that the focus of the selected papers is on multi-objective optimization, there is a scarcity of details regarding the utilized models. Frequently, they are merely mentioned superficially. This aspect warrants consideration to enhance the clarity of the results obtained from the multi-objective optimization of OurMED demo sites. (AlZahrani et al., 2016; Abdullah et al., 2018; Dai et al., 2018; Tayebikhorami et al., 2019; Aalami et al., 2020; Norouzi Khatiri et al., 2020; H. Wang et al., 2023).

- **Datasets**

As with the decision variables and the tools, the datasets employed are scarcely elaborated in the papers. Hence, we had to invest effort in identifying them based on the tools utilized and the objectives and outcomes attained. Table 2 brings a list of primary datasets that could potentially address issues similar to those presented in the selected papers.

Table 2 Primary datasets identified in papers related to water resource optimization.

Primary Datasets		
Aquifer parameters (e.g., hydraulic conductivity, transmissivity, porosity, storativity)	Groundwater recharge (e.g., precipitation, infiltration rates)	Sediment
Demands for different sectors	Groundwater use data (e.g., pumping rates, water abstraction)	Socioeconomic data (population, economic activity)
Disaster records (floods, droughts, landslides)	Historical climate	Soil properties
Economic data (e.g., agricultural production, water extraction, gross product)	Humidity	Streamflow
Environmental policy	Hydrogeological cross-sections	Temperature
Evapotranspiration	Hydrogeological maps (e.g., aquifer maps, hydrogeological units)	Topographic data
Future climate projections	Irrigation schedules	Vegetation Indices (NDVI, EVI)
Geological and hydrogeological maps and Reports	Land use and land cover	Water allocation
Groundwater exploration (e.g., drilling logs, test pumping data)	Precipitation	Water body (e.g., lakes, reservoirs, wetlands)

Primary Datasets		
Groundwater flow (e.g., hydraulic gradients, flow direction)	Remote Sensing ((e.g., satellite imagery, aerial photographs)	Water quality (e.g., pH, dissolved oxygen, nutrients, contaminants)
Groundwater monitoring (e.g., long-term monitoring wells)	Reservoir operations	Well Inventory
Groundwater quality (e.g., major ions, trace elements, contaminants)	River network	

- **Conflict resolution methods**

The use of conflict resolution methods was observed in 31% of the selected papers, with the Nash Bargaining Solution (from the game theory) being the most frequently employed method (RafipourLangeroudi et al., 2014; Nouri et al., 2015; Farhadi et al., 2016; Safavi et al., 2016; Tarebari et al., 2018; Y. Xu et al., 2019; Yazdian et al., 2021; Far & Ashofteh, 2024).

3.6. Case studies

In Table 3 we briefly introduce four case studies identified in the literature. These studies played a pivotal role in shaping discussions during the development of the multi-objective optimization methodology within the OurMED project.

Table 3 Examples of case studies about water resources optimization.

Case Study 1	
Country	Iran
Scale	Sub-basin - Najaf-Abad
Sectors	Drinking, industrial, agricultural, and environmental
Main problems	The Najaf-Abad sub-basin faces a complex water management challenge due to declining groundwater levels, reduced rainfall, and intricate interactions with the Zayandeh-Rud River. Drought has led to increased reliance on groundwater, causing a sharp drop in levels and reduced well productivity in some areas.
Objective functions	Maximizing the percentage of supplied demands during the simulation period. Minimizing groundwater extraction during the operation period.

Decision variables	The rate of extraction of groundwater and surface water for different demands.
Constraints	The water allocation priority follows an order of drinking, industrial, agricultural, and environmental demands. After surface water allocation, the remaining water demands will be supplied by groundwater.
Tools and Approaches	System dynamics, NSGA-II, and the Nash conflict resolution model.
Main results	The study found that the optimal water supply reached 16.84 million cubic meters, while the optimal reduction of the aquifer's water table was 0.63 meters, marking a 30% enhancement from the current state.
Source	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.146026 (Naghdi et al., 2021b)
Case Study 2	
Country	China
Scale	Basin- middle and lower Han River basin
Sectors	Domestic, industrial, and agricultural
Problems	Despite ample water resources, most rainfall occurs from May to October, leading to seasonal deficits. The main problem is the irregular temporal and spatial distribution of water resources.
Objective Functions	Maximizing economic efficiency. Maximizing the water allocation equity.
Decision Variables	Discharge of each reservoir. Water use in a sector and a water intake zone.
Constraints	The water use in a sector and a water intake zone should be less than the available water in that zone.** The change in storage capacity is captured by the water balance. The real-time storage capacity of a reservoir is constrained by the maximal and minimal storage capacity. The discharge of a reservoir in a water intake zone should be less than its discharge capacity. The water use in a sector and a water intake zone should be less than the water demand of a water use sector in a water intake zone. The discharge and the water use should not be less than zero. ** <i>The minimum ecological water demand is considered for water resources allocation, and the instream flows</i>

	<i>(ecology sustainability) are guaranteed first and then the remaining water is allocated into different water use sectors and regions.</i>
Tools and Approaches	Water supply data, hydrological data, demands (Quota and Tennant methods), Gini coefficients, NSGA-II
Main results	The findings suggest that the Pareto front effectively captures the trade-off between efficiency and equity in allocating water resources. Selecting the best alternative through the cost performance method can offer valuable insights for integrated water resources planning and management.
Source	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-021-04734-2 (Deng et al., 2022)
Case Study 3	
Country	Australia
Scale	Hypothetical irrigation area (data from Berembed Weir on Murrumbidgee River)
Sectors	Agricultural, economic, environmental
Problems	Conflicts between profitability, variable costs of production and pumping of groundwater and the complexity of considering environmental flows in addition to those concerning urban and agricultural water demand.
Objective Functions	Maximizing net returns (NR). Minimizing variable cost (VC). Minimizing total supplementary groundwater pumping requirements (TP) to meet crop demand from the irrigated areas.
Decision Variables	Total cost of water per unit volume. Cost of groundwater pumping. Variable cost (e.g., fertilizer and pesticide applications). Area of crop c. Water requirement for each crop (select a mix of crops). The volume of groundwater pumped for crop c.
Constraints	Crop water use in the irrigation areas should not exceed the total allocation in a given month. Environmental flows in each month should equal or exceed target flows. Total pumping (TP) from the irrigation area in any month should be less than or equal to allowable pumping.
Tools and Approaches	Hydrological and crop data, Irrigation water supply, demand and environmental requirement, and economic data. The weighted version of the goal

	programming model (WGP). The General Algebraic Modeling System (GAMS).
Main results	The study demonstrated how changes in ET and rainfall affect natural resources, crop areas, and water allocation. Adjusting goal weights significantly influenced optimal crop areas and target achievement. Tailoring decision variables for different seasons could aid policy decisions.
Source	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2005.06.013 (Xevi & Khan, 2005b)
Case Study 4	
Country	Iran
Scale	Plain (Loor-Andimeshk) - Balarood river
Sectors	Agricultural, drinking, and industrial
Problems	Due to the Balarood river's seasonal nature and its reduced surface water flow over six months, effective planning is essential for allocating water from both surface and groundwater sources after the construction of a dam.
Objective Functions	Maximizing the demand site coverage (%). Minimizing the groundwater drawdown (meters).
Decision Variables	The percentage of extraction from the surface water resource. The percentage of extraction from groundwater resources.
Constraints	The total amount of water allocated = SW + GW (sector, zone, and time). Demand for a specific sector should not exceed the total amount of SW allocated for all sectors. The total amount of GW to be extracted should not exceed the total deficiency for a specific sector (demand - total amount of surface water allocated).
Tools and Approaches	WEAP-MODFLOW, NSGA-II
Main results	The optimal allocation resulted in high-demand coverage and contributed to reducing the groundwater drawdown at the end of the operational period.
Source	http://dx.doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)WR.1943-5452.0001189 (Zeinali et al., 2020)

Conclusions

The concerns over widespread ecosystem pollution, climate change impacts, subsequent declines in freshwater availability, and the increasing need for transboundary water management, remain as critical and pertinent topics today. These issues emphasize the relevance of considering Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) as a comprehensive and holistic framework that encompasses multi-objective and multi-sectoral approaches as integral components. For that reason, it has become a prevalent and recommended management approach over the last four decades.

This literature review aimed to present the primary concepts of optimization and the most popular techniques to solve water resources optimization problems, focusing on multi-objective optimization, which are fundamental for IWRM. Classical methods as well as most recent evolutionary and swarm-based algorithms were presented.

Three of most popular classical methods were covered, such as the Linear Programming, Non-Linear Programming and Dynamic Programming, which are usually applied to solve single optimization problems, although they can be used in conjunction with scalarization techniques to solve MOP, usually introducing weight parameters to each objective or somehow by considering value judgments and preferences into the optimization process. Still, these methods are usually used to solve simpler optimization problems while more complex constrained, multi-dimensional and multimodal problems are often solved with multi-objective population-based algorithms.

Regarding MOEAs, Dominance-based, Indicator-based and Decomposition-based algorithms were included. The first one follows a straightforward design principle, requiring only a few parameters in its framework, and it can easily solve up to three objective functions. However, it might be difficult to solve more than 3 objectives (MaOP) and achieve a very regular spacing of solutions, and to measure convergence of the algorithm. NSGA-II is the most popular among them in water resources applications, being used in 74% of case studies papers analyzed in this literature review. There have been developing many efficient variants and hybrid versions which take advantage of different algorithm framework to achieve specific characteristics and results. Some variants can solve MaOP at the cost of diversity.

The indicator-based MOEAs like SMS-EMOA and HypE are mainly used to assess the convergence behavior of an algorithm, i.e., measure of the quality of Pareto front approximations to determine the consistency of a Pareto-optimal set, and when decision-makers want to include implicit preferences in the optimization process. However, they tend to increase computational cost as estimation time increases exponentially with the solution dimension and the number of objectives.

The decomposition-based algorithms such as MOEA/D and NSGA-III provide a very flexible framework which facilitate the use of hybrid algorithms for improved results, usually considering decision-makers implicit preferences, as they can take advantage of several scalarization techniques. They also can solve MaOP efficiently with minimal change when conducting the selection of solutions. Nevertheless, it might be difficult to

input required additional parameters if compared to other MOEAs, decision-making process becomes more difficult as the number of solutions increases, and it may depend on predefined reference points provided by experts to select solutions.

In respect to the swarm-based optimization algorithms, MOPSO is one of the most popular in water resources applications among many existing variants, which was used in 21% of the papers analyzed in this literature review. Simplicity and flexibility are its main advantages. Besides it is also a powerful technique for solving multi-objective, non-linear, multimodal, and complex optimization problems with fast convergence and low computational costs. Despite that, it is usually worse finding Pareto solutions than evolutionary algorithms, and the dependency of tuning parameters could be a drawback.

It should be noted that there is no method that can solve any optimization problem, but the characteristics of each one must be evaluated, as well as the data availability and the type of solutions desired, to choose a more appropriate method.

In addition to optimization methods mentioned above, simulation software should also be employed in the multi-sectoral water management (MSWM) approach in the sense that optimization is used as a preliminary screening tool to find a reasonable number of solutions and alternatives to the problem, which are further evaluated and improved by accurate simulations of the system. Aquatool, WEAP, MODFLOW, MIKE SHE, SWAT and MODSIM are some of the most popular and efficient software packages to simulate water resources components, some of which also consider optimization at some point of the modeling process.

For IWRM approach, one should also consider using some conflict resolution method to handle conflicting objectives and controversial opinions among stakeholders, which would help choosing the final decision among the alternatives available. The Nash Bargaining Solution was the most frequently employed method among analyzed papers.

Finally, although this literature review covered a variety of concepts, methods and case studies related to multi-objective optimization for integrated and multi-sector water resources management, there is a diversity of algorithms and other techniques that were not covered, e.g. system dynamics approach and machine learning techniques, but they can be quite relevant to the topic in question. Such techniques could improve the performance and efficiency of models, considering other social and economic aspects in a more integrated and automated approach.

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